

NEANIAS

Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Challenges

Document: D10.6 Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

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Editor(s)	Daniel Martínez (RICOH)		
Authors (s)	Daniel Martínez (RICOH), Javier Ramirez (RICOH), Bernat Olive (RICOH), Philip Bodare (ATHENA), Effie Zafeirakopoulou (NKUA), Eleni Petra (NKUA)		
Contributor (s)	Kakaletris Georgios (CITE), Eva Sciacca (INAF), Filomena Bufano (INAF), Cristobal Bordiu (INAF), Ugo Becciani (INAF), Katalin Kovacs (INNOMINE), Ioannis Neokosmidis (INCITES), Josep Quintana (CORONIS), Laura Vettorello (MEE0), Jozsef Kovacs (SZTAKI), Mel Krokos (UOP), Paul Wintersteller (TELEDYNE), Giuseppe Vizzari (UNIMIB) Angelo Pio Rossi (JACOBSUNI), Jafar Anbar (AMU, Jean-Christophe Sourisseau (AMU), Claudio Pisa (GARR)		
Reviewer(s)	Kalliopi Baika (Universite d'Aix-Marseille)		
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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighbouring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

This document is the dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report, report on activities and achievements of WP10 of NEANIAS project.

The work carried out in the WP10 framework focused on three main objectives: the communication (to increase NEANIAS visibility in terms of activities and outcomes, receive valuable feedback, inform the society and enhance market-uptake for the developed EOSC services), the dissemination (to position NEANIAS as a top-rank European Union EOSC project and EOSC Services Hub and to boost commercial exploitation strategy of the deployed EOSC services) and the user engagement and outreach (to share knowledge for further development and optimization of the considered services and raise awareness and demonstrate how NEANIAS services can cater to the needs and thematic end-user requirements).

Outreach task force has been in permanent and close contact with the entire consortium, managing the knowledge and project activities for communication, dissemination and engagement purposes. The activity is organized by means of four tasks to be carried out throughout the life of the project (month 1 to month 36) on a recurring basis: (i) communication, dissemination and outreach activities, (ii) branding, online presence and material establishment, (iii) stakeholder's engagement and (iv) Open Science initiatives and Research Infrastructures liaison activities with the support of all the partners according to their field of knowledge, specialty and connection with the ecosystem.

The document presents:

- The work plan for the work package, with goals and planned tasks.
- The report of activities carried out during the project's life, considering the digital channels, the material and templates, the articles and publications, the events and activities participated, and the open science initiatives and research infrastructures liaison activities.
- The WP 10 organization.
- The established KPIs and achievements.

1. Work Package 10

1.1. WP Objectives

The objectives of WP 10 Communication, Dissemination & Outreach are (i) to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work; (ii) to maximise the impactful visibility of project's work and achievements; (iii) to engage stakeholders that can support sustainability of the project via both update and feedback provisioning and can further empower the vision around EOSC and Open Science and (iv) to provide essential information and knowledge on the NEANIAS project to 3rd parties activating esp. in H2020 and EOSC landscape.

Its achievement was organised in four tasks, which are presented below.

1.2. WP Tasks

Below are presented the tasks to be carried out, according the grant agreement.

1.2.1. T10.1 Communication, dissemination and outreach activities

The task started with contribution to the Deliverable D10.1 plan of activities, identifying means and timeframe of activities, in combination with the work of T10.3, on stakeholder identification and targeting. The plan, constantly updated, is the road map for the activities of the work package in all directions. The task defines the outreach task force and assigns responsibilities for supervising and conducting activities. It also includes:

- Assignment and quality reviewing of blog posts and press releases that will be generated by invitation to respective project teams and partners.
- Actively support the promotion of the Open Calls of WP5, contribute to develop an appealing value proposition for the Open Calls and ensure that potential applicants are aware and apply.
- Track and report on the project of work, in foreseen reports as well as in internal meetings.
- Contribute to the relevant best practices essay issued by the WP participants.
- Production of interviews or webcasts on projects activities and achievements.
- Production of multimedia presentations with selection and editing of content provided by technical, business and research activities of the project.
- Produce project's newsletter on at least an annual basis.
- Delivery of scientific publications.

The task is led by NKUA with the support of all the partners.

The task progressed appropriately according to the evolution of the project. The content generation and review model has been defined, both of technical-scientific and general informative nature, and they have been published on the different platforms and on the NEANIAS website. The multimedia content, including demonstrators or broad-spectrum presentations, have been uploaded to the YouTube channel and promoted from all NEANIAS digital channels. Likewise, all the necessary resources have been made available to the Open Call for Innovation (more details in the Deliverable "D5.4 Open Call for Innovation, publication of open call offerings, rules for participation, criteria for selection and grants offered").

1.2.2. T10.2 Branding, online presence and material establishment

The task started with the delivery of visual and textual representation of the project to be used in project dissemination activities, considering the website, the digital channels, face to face or online presentations, events, and printed ones. It also delivered guidelines for promotion and use of materials delivered, as well as some guides and training material for its use. Apart from templates, the task delivered early in the project lifetime generic material for reuse in several face to face, printed and on-line occasions and in several languages. This material evolves in the course of the project, both for renewal of the project “face” but also as material matures around the deliveries of the technical and business work packages. The task included:

- establish the web site of the project, apply the branding of the project on its visuals, and maintain it for the duration of the project.
- establish 4 social media platform presence points, style them, monitoring and granting access as required.
- establish and operate mailing lists for newsletter, general and targeted communication.
- deliver and maintain templates for various documents and activities according to the needs.
- deliver baseline, generic content in the form of posters, leaflets and textual components.

The task is led by RICOH with the support of NKUA. The task was also supported by CITE, who technically contributed in shaping the document templates for reuse by the project and to a lesser degree to the launch of the web site and launched Facebook channel, as well as INAF who led the implementation of project’s logo.

All the activities pertaining to this task were carried out adequately during the project’s life, carrying out all the updates and revisions that the needs of the project as well as its partners required.

1.2.3. T10.3 Stakeholder’s engagement

The task started with the layout of an effective stakeholder engagement plan that allowed NEANIAS to locate and engage the targeted audience defined in the Communication, Dissemination, Engagement and outreach Plan and influencing individuals. The activities for engagement of stakeholders utilised the instruments provided by T10.1, that include, but are not limited to, email and web-based communication (focus on social media), generic promotion material, participation to events and conferences etc.

Furthermore, they expand on those with stakeholder-targeted

- material produced jointly with other project’s work package teams able to address a specific audience,
- events (workshops, sessions in conferences, meetings) planned for specific groups and
- establishment of interactions with key persons representing influential movements and organisations.

The task established the means for disseminating information inside the project, and mainly via internal reports and meeting sessions, the work done with stakeholders, and seeks to draw substantial feedback from them, in order to empower project's activities.

The process was largely boosted by the WP5 activities on Open Business Innovation Call and organises some events (workshops and parallel sessions in events) and work meetings that aimed to capture, in separate and joint occasions, all researchers from research sectors on boarded the project as well as innovators with business perspective.

The task also liaises with OpenAIRE to deliver thematic "portals" for access to Open Access knowledge for the communities engaged in the project.

The task is led by RICOH with the support of NOA, GARR, MEE0, INNOMINE, JUCOBSUNI, UNIMIB, AMU, SZTAKI, INAF, ATHENA, NKUA.

The global coronavirus pandemic (still active) impacted on face-to-face events, and many activities evolved towards digital. Attendance and participation in events, congresses, exhibitions, fairs and others was changed to virtual and the meetings were moved online. The main concern was the capacity to interact with individuals, resolved by the activity of thematic partners and their ability to involve their ecosystem and the ability of scientific partners to establish collaborations with other projects and innovation centres.

1.2.4. T10.4 Open Science initiatives and Research Infrastructures liaison activities

As NEANIAS seeks to maximize its impact and optimize the use of resources, an essential part is the establishment of liaison activities with initiatives/taskforces/projects that operate in the areas of Open Science, the EOSC and Research Infrastructures (including ESFRI and EOSC Hub satellite projects). The task seeks, locates and establishes the links with those initiatives, according to the plan, and monitors the result of those activities and reports back to all project structures regarding the progress and results of those activities. The task includes:

- Lay MoUs with that establish commitment for the work to be jointly performed.
- Plan and conduct joint meetings and participations to events.
- Organise other joint activities, such as workshops, demos, booths, papers etc.
- Stimulate the acquisition of feedback and adoption of both counterparts' results.
- Report on the outcome of the work perform and the benefits yielded for engaged parties.

The task is led by ATHENA with the support of GARR, JUCOBSUNI, RICOH, SZTAKI, INAF, NKUA.

Collaborative activities began to be fruitful when NEANIAS achieved its first project results, allowing knowledge, resources and challenges to be shared with other projects and organizations. All the activities, achievements and synergies established were communicated and disseminated through all NEANIAS channels.

1.3. Deliverables Planning

Project kick-off was the launch of dissemination activities, presenting the first generation of templates and organization of committees.

1.3.1. Deliverables Description

The deliverables of this WP are detailed below, specifying its codification, title and description:

- D10.1 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Draft), report on vision, strategy, and draft plan of opportunities, targets and outcomes expected and baseline dissemination material – regularly updated after delivery.
- D10.2 Project web site, site with visual alignment to the strategy with initial content.
- D10.3 Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report, report on 1st period activities and achievements of WP.
- D10.4 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final), updated / final strategy and activity plan.
- D10.5 NEANIAS open event, execution of one open event on NEANIAS (delivery up to 2 months after the date start).
- D10.6 Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report, summarizing all activities performed by WP and partners the results and feedback obtained by their audience / counterparts.

1.3.2. Deliverables timeline

Finally, the scheduling for deliverables is presented in the following table:

Code	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Month
D10.1	Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Draft	RICOH	Report	Public	2
D10.2	Project web site	RICOH	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	2
D10.3	Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report	RICOH	Report	Public	18
D10.4	Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)	RICOH	Report	Public	18
D10.5	NEANIAS open event	RICOH	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	35
D10.6	Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report	RICOH	Report	Public	36

Table 1 WP planning.

2. Report of activities

2.1. Digital channels

2.1.1. NEANIAS project website

NEANIAS established a dedicated website for the project (www.neanias.eu), applying the branding of the project on its visuals and keeping it updated considering both the content and the new features and integrations. The purpose of the website is to proactively promote the project and its final results by providing targeted information to various audiences within and beyond the project own community.

The design and development of NEANIAS portal was presented in a specific deliverable belonging to the same WP10. The web project was presented in the document “D10.2 Project Web Site” on month 2.

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) program faces the challenge of developing an agile, fit-for-purpose and sustainable service offering that can satisfy the evolving needs of the scientific community by stimulating the design and prototyping of novel innovative digital services.

NEANIAS (Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges) is an ambitious project that comprehensively addresses the challenges set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions.

NEANIAS will promote Open Science practices and play active role in the materialization of the EOSC ecosystem by efficiently engaging large scientific and professional communities; actively contributing to the technological, procedural, strategic and business development of EOSC. NEANIAS will drive the co-design and delivery of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: Underwater research, Atmospheric research and Space research, each engaging multitudinous academic and business groups, numerous researchers, professionals and governmental entities.

Fig. 1 NEANIAS website

The website has undergone various updates and technical, design and usability improvements, responding to the needs that have arisen during the life of the project or to promote events or actions of primary interest. Next figure shows a sample.

Fig. 2 NEANIAS website, new design

2.1.1.1. NEANIAS Web project

The NEANIAS site presents all the information related to NEANIAS, including:

- Information about the project: the goals, the challenges and the services to be offered.
- Information about the consortium and our organization, the work plan and our management.
- Dissemination and open access content: Articles, blog, collaborations, research, dissemination material, press and media references, public outcomes, publications.
- Mailing & Newsletters access and management.
- Acknowledgements and references.
- Events and activities, with updated information exhibitions about fairs, exhibitions, congresses, webinars, workshops, demos, ...
- Temporary dedicated sections to the NEANIAS Open Calls or the NEANIAS Open Event.
- News, with the latest information and updates.

- Service information (Contact information, GDPR, cookies policies, ...).

The website also acts as a reference contact point for any person interested in the projects, providing all the data to be contacted (including the created mail account):

Fig. 3 NEANIAS website as a reference contact point

From technical perspective, the website also hosts useful tools and features, such as:

- Embedded links to NEANIAS social networks accounts (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube).
- Gateways to allow the visitor to interact with NEANIAS social networks (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube) from their accounts in order to promote the endorsement and the dissemination.
- Really Simple Syndication service.
- Enhanced search engine.
- Labelling of content.
- Integration with e-mail.
- Newsletter management: contact subscription, management of preferences, un-subscription).
- Connection to others NEANIAS services.
- Integration with NEANIAS Open Call forms.

The website has been technically maintained (BBDD, backups, releases management, ...) and upgraded with new services as it became needed or requested.

2.1.1.2. Metrics

The website has been updated much more than once a week, as shown in the figure below. The objective was to be the point that collects and disseminates the main past or future events in the life of the project. The resulting figures reflect an intense, continuous and transversal work, far exceeding the initial commitments established in the Grant Agreement.

Fig. 4 website activity (month and accumulated)

Month 1 and month 2 corresponds to the web setup, with the project presentation. As the project activity grew, the website reflected all the work done.

An analytics account was created to track website activity. As a result, it can be stated that NEANIAS is well known in Europe and throughout the world. The following figures illustrate the impact of NEANIAS website, considering the country of access to NEANIAS website.

Fig. 5 Main visitors to NEANIAS website per country

Following the distribution of visitors considering the country (only the top 20 are shown).

Fig. 6 Distribution of website visitors per country (top-20)

2.1.2. Social media channels

NEANIAS established 4 social media platform presence points, styled them, granted access as required, and periodically tracked using tools built into each platform.

Social media channels have been constantly updated with relevant content, which made it possible to reach relevant groups through the communication and dissemination of information about news, achievements or any relevant event in an easy and fast way. Accessible to anyone who may be interested in NEANIAS, the social platforms are aimed at innovators, researchers, scientists, ICT specialists, businesspeople, policy makers, press, media, disseminators and the general public, promoting the engagement with NEANIAS.

A task of attracting and engaging followers is carried out, involving NEANIAS partners, the ecosystem and taking advantage of the events organized or participated by NEANIAS and its project members (conferences, congresses, workshops, webinars, fairs, exhibitions, etc. hackathons, etc.). ... Joint activities with other projects are also a means of attracting users.

The following social channels considered have been Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube. In order to make it easy to find and branding the project, all of them have a common name (**neanias_eu**) and are aligned to the project identity principles.

2.1.2.1. Twitter

An official account for NEANIAS has been created, managed and updated on twitter: **Neanias_eu**. The next figure shows the main page.

Fig. 7 NEANIAS Twitter Home page

The account has been used for short and quick messages to make the audience aware of any news or achievements, allowing them to interact with NEANIAS and offering them access to all the additional information on our website. Twitter has also been the best channel to connect with relevant stakeholders (including other European and H2020 projects) for cross promotion.

The next figure is an example and illustrates the analysis of relevant tweets.

Fig. 8 NEANIAS tweet (sample)

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Twitter served both to communicate project content and to interact with other users or agents and be endorsed by third parties, as well as to interact and engage the team, as it is illustrated in the next samples.

Fig. 9 NEANIAS project quoted and endorsed by other projects on Twitter

Fig. 10 NEANIAS, interacting with project members and ecosystem, and promoting national languages for local events

2.1.2.2. Facebook

An official account for NEANIAS has been created, managed and updated on Facebook: **Neanias_eu**. The next figure shows the main page.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 11 NEANIAS Facebook Home page

Facebook allowed us to communicate and disseminate in a similar way than Twitter, with longer messages and more detailed information. The following figure is an example and illustrates a representative publication.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 12 NEANIAS messages in Facebook (samples)

From Facebook, NEANIAS also participated in several groups to discuss topics of interest related to the project, be updated, and facilitate the promotion of activities and events, as shown in the next picture.

Fig. 13 Facebook groups participated by NEANIAS (sample)

2.1.2.3. LinkedIn

A NEANIAS group has been created, managed and updated on LinkedIn (**NEANIAS project**, www.linkedin.com/groups/13786081/) and a hashtag to promote any post (#neanias_eu). The next figure shows the main page.

Fig. 14 NEANIAS LinkedIn group

LinkedIn allowed us to communicate and disseminate in a similar way to Twitter, with longer messages and more detailed information, among much more professional profiles.

The following figures are some examples and illustrate representative publications. First, LinkedIn as a channel to disseminate NEANIAS news and achievements:

Fig. 15 NEANIAS post on LinkedIn group (sample)

Next, LinkedIn as a channel to interact and be endorsed by our stakeholders. In this case, Professor Paul D. Williams commenting on his participation in the NEANIAS Open Event, thus extending NEANIAS activity through new networks and audiences.

Fig. 16 NEANIAS post on LinkedIn group (sample 2)

2.1.2.4. YouTube channel

An official channel for NEANIAS was created, managed and updated on YouTube: **Neenias_eu**. The next figure shows the main page.

Fig. 17 NEANIAS channel on YouTube

The channel hosts all the multimedia content produced and recorded within the scope of NEANIAS.

Also, some playlists have been created to organize the content and make it easy for visitors to access:

- **Presentations:** Presentations about NEANIAS and its scope for all audiences.
- **Testimonials:** Feed-back and uses cases presentations from the ecosystem (industry, users, start-ups,) on NEANIAS services.
- **Demonstrations:** Presentations and technical and functional demonstrations of the NEANIAS services.
- **Conferences and events:** Conferences and presentations concerning NEANIAS, mainly for a scientific audience.
- **Webinars:** Training content concerning NEANIAS, mainly for a scientific and technical user.

The following figures are some examples and illustrate some representative videos.

Fig. 18 NEANIAS video on YouTube channel, providing information about the Open Call (sample)

Fig. 19 NEANIAS video on YouTube channel, presenting Space services (sample)

Fig. 20 NEANIAS video on YouTube channel, presenting an Underwater service (sample)

2.1.2.5. Tracking and metrics

NEANIAS activity in social networks has continued frequent and intense, both in the generation of content and in the interaction with followers and stakeholders. As a result, a high impact has been achieved, both in the ecosystem and in the general public, as illustrated in the following figures.

On twitter, 17 messages have been published on a monthly average during the project life, highly exceeding the project objectives. The monthly rate is closely related to project activity.

Fig. 21 NEANIAS tweets, monthly and accumulated

On M36, more than 330.000 tweet impressions have been achieved, exceeding the goal of 30.000 established by the end of the project. During the toughest months of the COVID-19 pandemic, activity on social media was especially intense. The figure below shows the monthly evolution.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 22 NEANIAS tweet impressions, monthly and accumulated

The analysis of the number of initial visitors to NEANIAS twitter profile is an indication of how the project arouses interest, as well as the extent to which it is becoming known. The impact is closely linked to relevant events (such as Hackathons, Open Calls, NEANIAS Open event, participation in events and congresses, ...).

Fig. 23 Visits to NEANIAS twitter profile, monthly and accumulated

Finally, an aggregated monthly analysis of NEANIAS followers by type of network. Unsurprisingly, Twitter and Facebook are the main ones. LinkedIn is not as widespread as they are, considering exclusively professional individual profiles. For its part, YouTube does not have many subscribed followers, since access to the channel is made when followers of other networks are notified of the publication of new multimedia content.

Fig. 24 NEANIAS followers, monthly and accumulated

Due to the global coronavirus pandemic, all face-to-face activities were severely restricted. To overcome this limitation, all the digital channels of the project were strengthened, and online activity was strongly reinforced.

All the previous figures show the results obtained. The following figure illustrates the impact obtained compared to what was planned at the beginning of the project under normal conditions.

Fig. 25 Impressions on Twitter. Obtained and planned

2.1.3. Mailing & Newsletter

NEANIAS established and operated a mailing list for newsletter for general and targeted communication.

2.1.3.1. Management

The management of the contact list is organized from the NEANIAS website. From a dedicated page, the mail services are offered to the audience, complying with the requirements of GDPR.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Any contact can request to be connected to NEANIAS populating a form that give us some information about the profiles of NEANIAS audience.

Fig. 26 Dedicated page on NEANIAS website for mailing purposes

Preference management (update, unsubscribe) can also be done from any email sent, which includes the information and a link in the footer.

Next, the figure illustrates the subscription form to NEANIAS newsletter. In any moment, the user can easily unsubscribe from the list. The form is integrated with NEANIAS mail engine, that saves all the provided information in a secure manner.

You are here: [Home](#) / [DISSEMINATION & OPEN ACCESS](#) / [Mailing & Newsletters](#) / [Subscribe](#)

Subscribe

Do you want to be informed about us? Please, subscribe to NEANIAS news.

(*) This data is needed.

Email Address *

First Name *

Last Name *

Organization

Position *

Website

Fields of interest

Underwater Research.
 Atmospheric Research.
 Space Research.
 Innovative IT services and solutions.
 Innovation & Open Science.
 Business.

Preferred format

HTML
 Plain-text

Contact permissions *

By providing us with your professional data, you agree that NEANIAS may contact you through the following channels for purposes related to the project. You can check our GDPR policies on NEANIAS website.

Newsletter / e-mail.

Fig. 27 Subscription form to NEANIAS Newsletter from NEANIAS website

2.1.3.2. Newsletters

Six newsletters have been published during the project's life, complying with the committed biannual rate. The production of newsletters includes the design of templates, IT configuration and integrations, the edition of content and the user management. The topics have been studied with the participation of all partners, presenting achievements, news, participation in events, general and scientific information and much more, considering the needs of the project stage (for instance, the Open Call was a main topic in Newsletter #3). General information about the project and the members was also provided.

Additional emails were also released to keep the audience updated with the latest news regarding specific activities (for example, the NEANIAS Open Event).

Following, some images illustrating the released newsletters.

Fig. 28 NEANIAS Newsletter 1 (extract)

Next, an extract from the 2nd release of NEANIAS newsletter:

The core services are the way that NEANIAS delivers functionalities within its systems architecture through decoupled functionalities composed by software and documentation. These services interact with each other in order to exchange data and provide the user some combined, higher-level functionality.

[Read more about NEANIAS core services.](#)

EOSC integration in NEANIAS's 1st year

NEANIAS project aims to develop and integrate services to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The objective is to share a set of thematic services with scientific researchers of EOSC communities on these fields. The NEANIAS service management system, which will support the design, development and delivery of NEANIAS services, has already been defined.

[Read more about NEANIAS EOSC Integration.](#)

NEANIAS at EOSC Project Expo: findings and award!

NEANIAS actively participated at EOSC Projects Expo. This joint event was organized as part of the Realizing the European Open Science Cloud by the EOSC-hub, FREYA and SBHOC projects, and was the first virtual exhibition showcasing initiatives and projects of the EOSC framework.

The event was very fruitful for NEANIAS. The exhibition provided us with many opportunities to present the challenges of NEANIAS and our services, both to the general and thematic public. We also had the opportunity to participate in the EOSC framework, to interact with the innovation ecosystem, make business contacts with potential stakeholders, stay updated through many interesting conferences and last, but not least, to promote open science initiatives and research infrastructures liaison with other projects. Furthermore, we were awarded!

[Read more about NEANIAS at EOSC Project Expo.](#)

More about us? NEANIAS Inside

NEANIAS is not only innovation and technology, but also the people who make it possible and the scientific community to which we address our work. We are pleased to publish this conversation with Simone Mantovani, Managing Director at Meteorological and Environmental Earth Observation (MEEEO) in order to make NEANIAS project better known from different perspectives.

Fig. 29 NEANIAS Newsletter 2 (extract)

Next, an extract from the 3rd release of NEANIAS newsletter:

NEANIAS launches its first Open Call for Atmospheric, Underwater and Space research

The first Open Call for the NEANIAS project was launched on February 8, 2021 in order to utilize the NEANIAS services, develop novel technologies and strengthen European researches in the Atmosphere, Underwater and Space service sectors. Apply to the NEANIAS Open Call if you intend to elaborate a concept of a novel technology and/or you intend to validate your start-up or your new development by working with leading European research institutions and companies!. The application ideas will be selected by NEANIAS experts representing the Atmospheric, Underwater and Space thematic areas.

A total of 24.000 € non-refundable support, of which at least 12.000 € will be allocated through this First Open Call, for each winner to support the work on their business case. The winners of the Open Call will also gain access to the infrastructure and knowledge base of NEANIAS and they will have the opportunity to work intensively with leading European institutions on their technology in a 3-months timeframe.

Everything you need to know about our Open Call

On NEANIAS Project website you can find anything you need to know about the Open Call. Please, [do not hesitate to visit us!](#) You can also follow us on [Twitter](#), [Facebook](#) and [LinkedIn](#) to stay updated! For any additional information on the Open Call you can also contact us and we will help you with any need you may have. We have a dedicated e-mail address for you: OpenCall@neanias.eu.

Online webinar for NEANIAS Open Call

NEANIAS team would like to invite you to an online webinar, taking place on the March-17, 2021 at 15:00h CET to present the project, the Open Call, the challenges, the awards, the application process, and everything you need to know about the Open Call.

What do you get?

Gain insider insight to current trends and emerging technology support for your research project, start-up and company. This webinar will give a first-hand look inside the application process, what is offered and the potential support opportunities through EU-funded initiative NEANIAS.

This is the programme:

- 15:00-15:10 Innomine Group is presenting the NEANIAS project and the aims of the Open Call of NEANIAS.
- 15:10 - 15:30 Representatives of the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space thematic areas talk about the aims of the Open Call, in technical terms.
- 15:30-16:00: Open questions.

The registration to the webinar is open until March-16, 2021, at noon. Interesting? Interested? Please, [sign up on our webinar registration form](#). It is free!

Open Call video Presentation

Do you want us to present the NEANIAS Open Call, the challenges, the awards and the application process? Do not miss this video presentation that explains everything you

Fig. 30 NEANIAS Newsletter 3 (extract)

Next, an extract from the 4th release of NEANIAS newsletter:

NEANIAS launches its 2nd Open Call for Atmospheric, Underwater and Space research

Do you have an incredible idea in the atmospheric, underwater and space research domains? We're touching base to share an opportunity you don't want to miss! **NEANIAS Consortium launches its 2nd Open Call!**

After the successful 1st NEANIAS Open Call, we would like to cordially invite more research teams, SME-s and start-ups to submit a proposal to receive professional expert support, validate innovative ideas and boost the development with NEANIAS Services and Experts for free!

Call for proposals opens for companies and teams of individual researchers to utilise the services developed within the NEANIAS project.

- **Call opening date:** 11 October 2021, at 9:00 Brussels local time.
- **Deadline of submission:** 8 December 2021, at 17:00 Brussels local time.
- **Expected duration of participation:** 3-6 Months, with expected start on the 1st of February 2022.

2nd NEANIAS Open Call
 Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Sciences
 in the European Open Science Cloud

Application deadline: Dec 8, 2021

NEANIAS

Everything you need to know about our Open Call

On [NEANIAS Project website](#) you can find anything you need to know about the Open Call. Please, [do not hesitate to visit us!](#)

You can also follow us on [Twitter](#), [Facebook](#) and [LinkedIn](#) to stay updated!

For any additional information on the Open Call you can also contact us and we will help you with any need you may have. We have a dedicated e-mail address for you: OpenCall@neanias.eu.

Online webinar for NEANIAS Open Call

The NEANIAS team would like to invite you to a webinar, taking place on the **4 November 2021, 16:00 h CET**, to present the project, the Open Call, the challenges, the services, the application process, the eligibility criteria, and everything you need to know about the Open Call.

Gain insider insight to current trends and emerging technology support for your research project, start-up and company. This webinar will give a first-hand look inside the application process, what is offered and the potential support opportunities through EU-funded initiative NEANIAS.

Discover [all the details of the webinar](#). You can also [sign up here](#). It is free!

Fig. 31 NEANIAS Newsletter 4 (extract)

Next, an extract from the 5th release of NEANIAS newsletter:

NEANIAS is pleased to invite you to the Project Open Event!

A free open event to present the results of the NEANIAS project, exploit the potential of its novel technological solutions and interconnect innovation, business, and the public sector. It will take place in Barcelona, on September 22 and 23, 2022.

Save the date!

The event is aimed at researchers, scientists, entrepreneurs, innovators, companies, investors, business developers, consultants, disseminators, public managers, and general public interested in Space, Underwater, Atmosphere and novel Information Technologies.

Find out everything at [NEANIAS Open Event](#).

You can also register [here](#).

NEANIAS Space services onboarded on EOSC

Four NEANIAS Space services are already onboarded on the European Open Science Cloud, available to the EOSC community. With this article we present more relevant information about them, and we invite you to discover their full potential.

Keep reading and find out more about [NEANIAS Space services](#).

NEANIAS Atmospheric services onboarded on EOSC

Three NEANIAS atmospheric services are onboarded on the European Open Science Cloud, so they are already available to the EOSC community. This article introduces its main features and all the details on how to discover them.

Learn more about [NEANIAS Atmosphere Services](#).

NEANIAS Underwater services onboarded on EOSC

The three NEANIAS Underwater services are onboarded on the European Open Science Cloud, and they are ready to the EOSC community. This article presents the most relevant information about them, as well as how to discover them.

Keep reading and learn more about [NEANIAS Underwater Services](#).

NEANIAS Core services onboarded on EOSC

Three NEANIAS Core services are onboarded on the European Open Science Cloud, available to

Fig. 32 NEANIAS Newsletter 5 (extract)

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Next, an extract from the 6th release of NEANIAS newsletter:

The NEANIAS Open Event will be soon, next Sept 22 and 23!

A free open event to present the results of the NEANIAS project, exploit the potential of its novel technological solutions and interconnect innovation, business, and the public sector. It will take place in Sant Cugat - Barcelona, on September 22 and 23, 2022.

Save the date!

The event is aimed at researchers, scientists, entrepreneurs, innovators, companies, investors, business developers, consultants, disseminators, public managers, and general public interested in Space, Underwater, Atmosphere and novel Information Technologies.

Find out everything at [NEANIAS Open Event](#).

All the registration details, [here](#).

Online attendees, stay in touch. The link for the online connection will be sent in the next few days.

The Mayoress of Sant Cugat, at the NEANIAS Open Event

The NEANIAS team is very proud to announce the participation of the **Il·lma. Bra. Mireia Inglà, Mayoress of Sant Cugat del Vallès**, at the NEANIAS event, accompanied by members of her management team (Economic Promotion, Employment, Business, Training and Commerce).

Likewise, representatives of the **strategy and innovation areas of the Government of Catalonia** will share their views on the opportunities that digital solutions can offer for the development of the information society and for the definition of innovative and efficient policies.

We will also meet with international **representatives of the EU's innovation programmes** to learn more about the European strategy and the EU's role in research.

Also, all our acknowledgment to the **companies** that participate, giving a market vision and presenting their success stories.

Thank you all very much for your support.

[Discover more about the agenda](#).

NEANIAS solutions and testimonials from the industry

Many companies are supporting the NEANIAS project by using its novel IT services, already available in the European Open Science Cloud. Likewise, they offer valuable collaboration through very important feed-back that facilitates the implementation of features according to the needs of the market and research.

[Find out more about some of them here!](#) You can also learn more about these innovative companies at the event, exchange experiences, and discover synergies and possible collaborations.

Fig. 33 NEANIAS Newsletter 6 (extract)

Finally, an excerpt from the footers of the NEANIAS newsletter, common to any release

Fig. 34 NEANIAS Newsletter. footer

2.2. Material and templates

2.2.1. NEANIAS identity

The first step was to create a digital identity and branding for NEANIAS by means of a logo.

Fig. 35 NEANIAS logo. The first one (on the left) and the new one (on the right)

The first one (on the left) was created for the proposal and used initially. The new, updated and more modern logo (on the right) was created later and replaces the previous one. Once the new logo was approved, all the templates were redone.

A dedicated logo was also created for each of the thematic areas of NEANIAS, Underwater, Atmospheric and Space, as shown below.

Fig. 36 NEANIAS logos for thematic areas

Additionally, the thematic services also have their own images:

Fig. 37 NEANIAS Atmospheric thematic services identity

Fig. 38 NEANIAS Space thematic services identity

Fig. 39 NEANIAS Underwater thematic services identity

Furthermore, for significant events, special designs have been developed. Following some examples.

Fig. 40 NEANIAS 1st Open Call design (1)

Fig. 41 NEANIAS 1st Open Call design (2)

Fig. 42 NEANIAS 2nd Open Call design

Fig. 43 NEANIAS Open Event design

2.2.2. Document templates

The WP10 team produced a set of templates for various documents and activities. All of them were maintained and updated according to the needs, hosting them in NEANIAS SharePoint and training the team for their use, as it is illustrated in the figure below:

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

✓	Type	Name	Modified	Modified by	Size
	Word Document	NEANIAS-Qnn-WPxx-Progress-Report.Template.docx	16/03/2020	Daniel Martinez Sala	41.54 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS-Mnn-PartnerID-Progress-Report.Template.docx	16/03/2020	Daniel Martinez Sala	49.77 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS-Milestone.Template.docx	16/03/2020	Daniel Martinez Sala	347.63 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS-Meeting-Minutes.Template.docx	16/03/2020	Daniel Martinez Sala	66.62 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS-Deliverable-Report.Template.docx	16/03/2020	Daniel Martinez Sala	407.80 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS-Deliverable-Other.Template.docx	30/03/2020	Kakaletris Georgios	347.97 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS-Deliverable-Document.Template.docx	08/01/2021	Effie Zafeirakopoulou	401.51 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS-Deliverable-Blog.Template.docx	06/05/2020	Kakaletris Georgios	284.34 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS-ActivityLog-PartnerID.Template.docx	25/06/2020	Kakaletris Georgios	46.56 KB ...
	Presentation	NEANIAS- Presentation - Template.pptx	13/03/2020	Daniel Martinez Sala	208.41 KB ...
	Word Document	NEANIAS_PeriodicReport_WP_template.docx	07/05/2021	Kakaletris Georgios	96.98 KB ...
	Excel Spreadsheet	NFANIAS Monitoring all partners.xlsx	07/05/2021	Kakaletris Georgios	71.55 KB ...

Fig. 44 Document templates on NEANIAS SharePoint

The application of the templates includes the following:

- Deliverables
- Report activities.
- Meetings
- Project presentations
- Baseline text for specific purposes (mailings, invitations, ...) related to any special need proposed by the project team.

In any templates the project graphics are applied as appropriate, customizing for particular purposes when necessary.

Next figure illustrates a “.ppt” template to be used in any activity related to the project. The current document is another example, edited from a project “.doc” template.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 45 Template for presentations

In addition, templates for special needs were also created. The example below illustrates a call for the Open Call.

Fig. 46 Open Call presentation

Below, a baseline text showing how to promote NEANIAS digital channels:

Dear colleagues,
 When sending e-mails, please do not miss the opportunity to promote NEANIAS and our social channels so that we can keep our audience connected, updated and engaged.
 You can also invite them to subscribe to our Newsletter and give us the opportunity to write to them from NEANIAS.
 Here is some text that you can use if you like. Maybe you can use it as the footer of your mail.
 Kind regards

www.neanias.eu

Do you wish to be updated on NEANIAS latest news? We can be connected through our social networks:

- Twitter: @Neanias_eu
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/neanias.eu>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13786081/>
- YouTube channel: Neanias_eu

We also have a mailing list. If you want to receive information about us, do not hesitate to subscribe to our Newsletter: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/dissemination-open-access/newsletters>

Feel free to join and follow us to learn everything about NEANIAS.

Fig. 47 baseline text provided to promote NEANIAS channels

2.2.3. Dissemination material

The WP produced, delivered and updated baseline generic content in the form of posters, leaflets and textual components. All the material is available on the project SharePoint.

Following, some samples:

Fig. 48 NEANIAS poster

Atmospheric Environment | **Underwater Environment** | **Space Astro/Planet**

NEANIAS

Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges

NEANIAS will promote Open Science practices and play active role in the materialization of the EOSC ecosystem by efficiently engaging large scientific and professional communities; actively contributing to the technological, procedural, strategic and business development of EOSC.

NEANIAS will drive the co-design and delivery of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: Underwater research, Atmospheric research and Space research, each engaging multitudinous academic and business groups, numerous researchers, professionals and governmental entities.

✓ Sustainable Innovative Services to the Research Communities

Address community specific needs for underwater, atmosphere and space research sectors	Nurture new business opportunities
Onboard communities to the Open Science, EOSC and interdisciplinary research era	Power-up EOSC

✓ Services - Infrastructures - Communities & Businesses

<p>Underwater Environment Atmospheric Environment Space Astro/Planet</p> <p>Co-design, Innovative Thematic Services Tailored to Specific Data Cycle Processes</p>	<p>Develop/Integrate Cross-Cutting Core & Thematic Services at EOSC</p> <p>EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD</p> <p>OpenAIRE</p> <p>ESFRI</p> <p>EGI</p> <p>EOSC hub</p> <p>EOSC</p> <p>EUDAT</p> <p>Exploit Existing EOSC Services & the EU Open Science Ecosystems</p>	<p>Engage User Communities</p> <p>Underwater Space Atmospheric</p> <p>+ Additional Cases</p> <p>NEANIAS Innovation Hub</p>
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✓ Business & Sustainability Outlook

<p>Strong orientation to industry & business 5 SME partners 2 Enterprise partners</p> <p>Focus on business planning: market analysis, cost analysis, legal and ethical issue analysis etc.</p>	<p>Two business innovation cases from SMEs Energy Smart Cities</p> <p>Strong external innovation motivation Open Innovation Calls Linking to innovation hubs Provisions for datathons and hackathons with prizes and incubations</p>
--	--

Participants

NEANIAS receives funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.101017449

Fig. 49 NEANIAS banner (1)

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 50 NEANIAS banner (2)

Fig. 51 NEANIAS leaflet

In addition, dissemination material is offered on the website for public uses.

Fig. 52 Downloadable public dissemination material on NEANIAS website

The dissemination material was also deployed in meetings and face-to-face events, thus helping to consolidate the project's brand. Unfortunately, the impact of the global COVID-19 pandemic limited this type of act for many months, with digital documents being the main dissemination and promotion tool. Figures below show some dissemination material used in face-to-face events.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 53 Dissemination and branding material for face-to-face events

Fig. 54 Dissemination and branding material for face-to-face events: accreditations, notebook, sheets, pen

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 55 Dissemination and branding material for face-to-face events: leaflets

Fig. 56 Dissemination and branding material for face-to-face events: folder, sheets and envelope

Fig. 57 Dissemination and branding material for face-to-face events: balls, pens

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 58 Dissemination and branding material for face-to-face events: roll-up

Fig. 59 Banner in the NEANIAS Open Event

2.2.4. Material for internal training

Presentations and content have been made, used for internal meetings and training, regarding the use of digital tools and platforms as well as the development of the team's capacities in communication and dissemination issues. The material has been proactively created based on the needs identified.

Following, some examples:

- Guide with recommendations for organizing online events.

Fig. 60 Training material. Help guide to host an online hackathon

- Guide to empower people in NEANIAS digital channels

Fig. 61 Training material. Twitter Help guide for NEANIAS team

2.3. Articles and publications

Article and publication production includes general purpose articles, press and media content, and scientific publications. The primary language is English in order to reach the widest potential audience. However, content into other languages (Italian, Spanish, French, Greek, German, Portuguese, Catalan, Hungarian, Slovak) has also been generated (22 articles). The website hosts all the work generated.

2.3.1. Articles of general purpose

The project published 364 articles of general interest that may be distributed over the press, other media sites, including project news, collaborations, outputs or achievements. The work is aimed to reach the general public, related initiatives, research groups or technology providers.

Fig. 62 Production of articles

The articles can be organized within the following categories:

- General information: content for both a general public and target sectors (underwater, atmospheric, space, ICT) presenting and analysing about research, open science, astronomy, cloud, business, innovation, project achievements, NEANIAS inside, machine learning, co-creation, among others. Each article has been done using the most appropriate format (article, interview, video-blog, ...). Following, some illustrative examples:
 - *“Cloud-Based Visual Discovery in Astronomy: Novel EOSC Services for Exploring Large Scale Catalogues”*.
 - *“Core Services foundation and implementation”*.
 - *“[IT] L’astrofisica di nuova generazione: tra sfide e opportunità”*.
 - *“How to host an online Hackathon? launch and management”*.
 - *“NEANIAS inside. A chat with our Project Coordinator”*.

Those articles of scientific interest are also offered in downloadable pdf format, with the look & feel of the project, as displayed below:

The screenshot shows the NEANIAS website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for HOME, NEWS, ABOUT THE SITE, and CONTACT US, along with a search bar. Below the navigation, a breadcrumb trail reads: You are here: Home / DISSEMINATION & OPEN ACCESS / Articles & Blog / What is Mars made of? On the left side, there is a sidebar menu with expandable sections: PROJECT (About NEANIAS, Services), CONSORTIUM, ORGANIZATION (Work Plan, Management), DISSEMINATION & OPEN ACCESS (Articles & Blog, Collaboration & Research, Material, Mailing & Newsletters), and TAGS (Space Research, Astronomy). The main content area features the article title "What is Mars made of?" and a brief introduction: "NEANIAS to help interactive exploration of Mars composition via spectral data access." It then discusses planetary science and geologic diversity. A "Read the full article" link is provided. The article is dated July 2020 and has a rating of five stars. Social media icons for Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook are visible at the bottom right.

Fig. 63 Article on NEANIAS website, ready to be downloaded

The screenshot shows a PDF document from NEANIAS. The header includes the NEANIAS logo, the text "Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Challenges", and the date "2020 July". The main text discusses Mars' surface geology and the challenges of interpreting data, mentioning "uncertainties" and "address the composition". Below the text is a color-composite image of Mars. The image is a square-shaped view showing a rugged, cratered landscape with a mix of red, green, and blue hues. To the left of the image, technical details are provided: "Location: Hill Fossae", "Dataset: 2008_172-fr1000064d9", and "Browse Products: VNIR enhanced color composite". To the right, there are coordinates: "R: 8660", "C: 8530", and "B: 8660". A scale bar at the bottom right of the image indicates a distance of 2 km. Below the image, a caption reads: "Figure 3: Exemplary Red-Green-Blue color-composite view of an area of Mars displaying surface compositional variability." The text continues to discuss visualization services (NEANIAS S1), mosaicking and map-making (NEANIAS S2), and machine learning (NEANIAS S3). It concludes by mentioning the Europlanet Planetary Science Research Infrastructure (RI) and its geologic mapping activities. The authors are listed as "A.P. Rossi, C. Brandt, G. Nodjoumi" from "Jacobs University Bremen". At the bottom, there are two footnotes: ⁵ <https://www.europlanet-society.org/europlanet-2024-ri/> and ⁶ <https://www.europlanet-society.org/europlanet-2024-ri/gmap/>.

Fig. 64 NEANIAS article in downloadable pdf format, with NEANIAS identity

- Press and media: Presentations and comments on the presence of NEANIAS in the media at the European level. Following, some illustrative examples:
 - *“NEANIAS Project is presented in Hydrographische Nachrichten, a journal of applied Hydrography”*
 - *“NEANIAS project and its proposal in the monitoring and forecasting of air quality in the cities was introduced in Noticias de Aveiro. The article is written in Portuguese”.*
 - *“NEANIAS Project and the challenges of the data management in the research and the innovation were presented in CloudComputing-Insider, a trademark of the Vogel Communications Group. The article is written in German.*
 - *“NEANIAS Project was presented with the article "New Knowledge through international Data Exchange: A Cloud for Marine, Atmospheric and Planetary Researchers" in IDW Magazine”.*
 - *“The NEANIAS Project and its application for the smart cities in the European Open Science Cloud was presented in WattsOn Portugal. The article is written in Portuguese”.*
- News and findings from events and activities: on the website NEANIAS team presented and analysed the activity, main findings and results of the congresses, conferences, events, workshops, fairs, etc. participated. Following, some illustrative examples:
 - *“NEANIAS presented at Milano Digital Week”.*
 - *“NEANIAS attended the e-Infrastructures Reflection Group workshop (e-IRG)”.*
 - *“NEANIAS awarded at EOSC Project Expo”.*
 - *“NEANIAS at the XXX Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems (ADASS) Conference”.*
 - *“NEANIAS at EOSC Landscape Final Validation Workshop”.*
- Collaboration and research, presenting collaborations in research and even research positions for the project. Following, some illustrative examples:
 - *“NEANIAS at the University of Malta”.*
 - *“NEANIAS at Greek's Space Center Management Board”.*
 - *“NEANIAS presented at the University of Cape Town”.*
 - *“NEANIAS at ENTA laboratories (Environmental and Networking Technologies and Applications)”.*
 - *“Post Doc position for research in astrophysics”.*

2.3.2. Press releases and media

The press releases offered general purpose announcements and publications to the public disseminated via web site as well as electronic and printed press. This media aimed to reach the widest possible audience (general public, funders and other not connected stakeholders).

Next table summarizes the NEANIAS presence in the media (more details on the NEANIAS website).

Media	Date	Country	Language
Press Conference: "The impacts of climate change on Greek airports"	10/01/2020	UK	English
TO BHMA News	13/01/2020	Greece	Greek

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IDW Magazine	16/01/2020	UK	English
Cloud Computer Insider	07/02/2020	Germany	German
IOTBDS	10/05/2020	UK	English
Coralia News	12/06/2020	Greece	Greek
Deutschland.de	09/07/2020	Germany	German
We Electric Magazine	31/10/2020	Portugal	Portuguese
OACT	17/12/2020	Italy	English
GARR News	20/12/2020	Italy	Italian
Noticias de Aveiro	29/12/2020	Portugal	Portuguese
BIT Magazine	30/12/2020	Portugal	Portuguese
WattsOn	31/12/2020	Portugal	Portuguese
SmartCities Magazine	05/01/2021	Portugal	Portuguese
La List	22/01/2021	France	French
Universitat de Girona	25/02/2021	Spain	Catalan
Hydrographische Nachrichten Journal	03/03/2021	Germany	English
iNewsgr	29/10/2021	Greece	Greek
Naftemporiki	29/10/2021	Greece	Greek
EL News	29/10/2021	Greece	Greek
Business News	29/10/2021	Greece	Greek
ICTCluster	01/11/2021	Bulgaria	Bulgarian
ASEITEC	16/11/2021	Spain	Spanish
ASEITEC	16/11/2021	Spain	Catalan
ASEITEC	16/11/2021	Spain	French
ASEITEC	16/11/2021	Spain	English
ASEITEC	16/11/2021	Spain	German
Smart Catalonia	16/11/2021	Spain	Catalan
Barcelona.dot	17/11/2021	Spain	Catalan
Enterprise Europe Network	22/11/2021	Spain	Spanish
EMEA startups	24/01/2022	International	English
startup.gr	08/09/2022	Greece	Greek
ESADE	15/09/2022	Spain	Spanish
Eraportal	16/09/2022	Slovakia	Slovak
Veda a Technika	19/09/2022	Slovakia	Slovak
OpenAire	19/09/2022	International	English
Smart Catalonia	19/09/2022	Spain	Catalan
DTUH.gr	19/09/2022	Greece	Greek
Cugat.Cat	22/09/2022	Spain	Catalan

Table 2 NEANIAS presence on media

Next, some illustrative images:

Fig. 65 Some samples of NEANIAS in media: journal (left) and newspaper (right)

2.3.3. Scientific publications

Scientific publications consider research publications in international top-rank journals and conferences in diverse fields that span Archaeology, Geology, Astrophysics, Planetary Science, Computer Science, Geoscience, Renewable Energy, Climate, and Atmospheric research. Addressed to targeted interest groups in research, business and technology, among others.

Following the peer reviewed articles produced during the project’s life:

Title	Author	Publisher	Date
New frontiers in computing and data analysis—the European perspectives.	Becciani, Ugo, and C. Petta.	Radiation Effects and Defects in Solids 174.11-12 (2019): 1020-1030.	2019
The Virtual Observatory ecosystem facing the European Open Science Cloud	Marco Molinaro, Mark Allen, Françoise Genova, André Schaaff, Margarida Castro Neves, Markus Demleitner, Sara Bertocco, Dave Morris, François Bonnarel, Stelios Voutsinas, Catherine Boisson, Giuliano Taffoni	SPIE Astronomical Telescopes + Instrumentation, 2020, Online Only	2020

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Selfie Drones for 3D Modelling, Geological Mapping and Data Collection: Key Examples from Santorini Volcanic Complex, Greece.	Bonali, F.; Antoniou, V.; Vlasopoulos, O.; Tibaldi, A. and Nomikou, P.	Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Geographical Information Systems Theory, Applications and Management - GISTAM ISBN 978-989-758-425-1 ISSN 2184-500X, pages 119-128. DOI: 10.5220/0009575001190128	2020
Seafloor mapping from multispectral multibeam acoustic data at the European Open Science Cloud	Mertikas P., Karantzalos K.,	ISPRS - International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences	2020
Towards Porting Astrophysics Visual Analytics Services in the European Open Science Cloud.	Sciacca E. et al.	Arai K., Kapoor S., Bhatia R. (eds) Intelligent Computing. SAI 2020. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, vol 1230. Springer, Cham.	2020
Parallel and Distributed Training of Deep Neural Networks: A brief overview.	Attila Farkas, Gábor Kertész and Róbert Lovas	2020 IEEE 24th International Conference on Intelligent Engineering Systems (INES)	2020
Machine learning methods in Smartphone-Based Activity Recognition	István Pintye	SACI 2020 - IEEE 14th International Symposium on Applied Computational Intelligence and Informatics DOI: 10.1109/SACI49304.2020.9118784	2020
Big data and machine learning framework for clouds and its usage for text classification	István Pintye, Eszter Kail, Péter Kacsuk and Róbert Lovas	Wiley Online Library	2020
Mapping and evaluating kinematics and the stress and strain field at active faults and fissures: A comparison between field and drone data at the NE rift, Mt Etna (Italy).	Tibaldi, A., Corti, N., De Beni, E., Bonali, F. L., Falsaperla, S., Langer, H., Neri, M., Cantarero, M., Reitano, D., Fallati, L.	Solid Earth, 12, 801–816, 2021	2021
Astronomical source finding services for the CIRASA visual analytic platform	S. Riggi and C. Bordiu and F. Vitello and G. Tudisco and E. Sciacca and D. Magro and R. Sortino and C. Pino and M. Molinaro and M. Benedettini	Astronomy and Computing	2021

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

	and S. Leurini and F. Bufano and M. Raciti and U. Becciani		
Semantic Segmentation of Radio-Astronomical Images	Carmelo Pino, Renato Sortino, Eva Sciacca, Simone Riggi & Concetto Spampinato	Hernández Heredia, Y., Milián Núñez, V., Ruiz Shulcloper, J. (eds) Progress in Artificial Intelligence and Pattern Recognition. IWAIPR 2021. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 13055. Springer, Cham.	2021
Production Machine Learning Frameworks for Geospatial Big Data	Ntouskos V, Iliopoulou C, Karantzas K	IEEE International Conference on Big Data,	2021
The Volcanic Relief within the Kos-Nisyros-Tilos Tectonic Graben at the Eastern Edge of the Aegean Volcanic Arc, Greece and Geohazard Implications	Nomikou P, Krassakis P, Kazana S, Papanikolaou D, Koukouzas N	Geosciences	2021
Evaluating explainable artificial intelligence methods for multi-label deep learning classification tasks in remote sensing	Kakogeorgiou, I., Karantzas, K.	International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation	2021
Defining and Detecting Complex Changes on RDF Knowledge Bases	Galani, T., Papastefanatos, G., Stavrakas, Y. et al.	J Data Semant	2021
The NEANIAS Project: Bathymetric mapping and processing goes cloud	Paul Wintersteller, Nikolaos Foskolos, Christian Ferreira, Konstantinos Karantzas, Danai Lampridou, Kalliopi Baika, Jafar Anbar, Josep Quintana, Stergios Kokorotsikos, Claudio Pisa, Paraskevi Nomikou.	Hydrographische Nachrichten Journal	2021
Real-time Web-based Remote Interaction with Active HPC Applications	Tim Dykes, Ugo Varetto, Claudio Gheller, Mel Krokos	IVAP	2021
Evolutionary Map of the Universe (EMU): Compact radio sources in the Scorpio field towards the Galactic plane.	Riggi, S., et al.	Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society	2021
A new view of observed galaxies through 3D modelling and visualisation.	Dykes, T., Gheller, C., Koribalski, B. S., Dolag, K., & Krokos, M.	Astronomy and Computing, 2021, 34, 100448.	2021
Supporting FAIR Principles in the Astrophysics Community: the European Experience	Marco Molinaro, Mark Alle, François Bonnardel, Françoise Genova, Markus Demleitner, Kay Graf, Dave Morris, Enrique Solano, André Schaaff	Cornell University	2021

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Cloud-agnostic architectures for machine learning based on Apache Spark.	Enikő Nagy Róbert Lovas István Pintye Ákos Hajna IPéter Kacsuk	Advances in Engineering Software. Volume 159, September 2021, 103029	2021
Unsupervised Data Pattern Discovery on the Cloud	Cecconello, T., Puerari, L., & Vizzari, G.	AlxIA 2021 Discussion Papers - co-located with the 20th International Conference of the Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence (AlxIA2021). CEUR Workshop Proceedings Vol. 3078	2022
Scientific Visualization on the Cloud: the NEANIAS Services towards EOSC Integration	Eva Sciacca, Mel Krokos, Cristobal Bordiu, Carlos Brandt, Fabio Vitello, Filomena Bufano, Ugo Becciani, Mario Raciti, Giuseppe Tudisco, Simone Riggi, Eugenio Topa, Sami Azzi, Benjamin Kyd, Simone Mantovani, Laura Vettorello, Jiacheng Tan, Josep Quintana, Ricard Campos, Noela Pina	Journal of Grid Computing volume 20, Article number: 7	2022
First Detection of Silicon-bearing Molecules in η Car	C Bordiu, JR Rizzo, F Bufano, G Quintana-Lacaci, C Buemi, P Leto, F Cavallaro, L Cerrigone, A Ingallinera, S Loru, S Riggi, C Trigilio, G Umana, E Sciacca	The Astrophysical Journal Letters, Volume 939, Number 2. DOI 10.3847/2041-8213/ac9b10	2022
MARIDA: A Benchmark for Marine Debris Detection from Sentinel-2 Remote Sensing Data	Kikaki K, Kakogeorgiou I, Mikeli P, Raitsos DE, Karantzas K.	PLOS One	2022
Seabed Classification from Multispectral Multibeam Data.	Mertikas et al.	IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering	2022
A new free software to calculate the tectonic stress trajectories.	Bonali F., Ntouskos, V., Gounari, O., Corti, N., Bressan S., Karantzas, K. and Tibaldi A.	Computers and Geosciences	In preparation
Latent Space Explorer: a Visual Analytics Tool for Pattern Discovery on the Cloud	Cecconello, T., Puerari, L., & Vizzari, G.	SoftwareX	In preparation

Table 3 Scientific publications

Next, an example of scientific publication:

Fig. 66 Scientific publication (sample)

All the articles were disseminated from NEANIAS social networks and published on the NEANIAS website, introducing the work, the authors, their affiliations, the abstract, the acknowledgements to NEANIAS and all the information about the publisher, as well as the link to download the work, as it is shown in the figures below:

Fig. 67 NEANIAS twitter announcing a new publication

- > PROJECT
- > About NEANIAS
- > Services
- > CONSORTIUM
- > ORGANIZATION
- > Work Plan
- > Management
- > DISSEMINATION & OPEN ACCESS
 - > Articles & Blog
 - > Collaboration & Research
 - > Material
 - > Mailing & Newsletters
 - > Press & Media
 - > Public outcomes
 - > Publications
- > ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS & REFERENCES
- > EVENTS & ACTIVITIES
- > OPEN CALL

A new view of observed galaxies through 3D modelling and visualisation.

The peer-review article "A new view of observed galaxies through 3D modelling and visualisation", by University of Portsmouth and collaborators, has been published in the journal *Astronomy and Computing*.

"A new view of observed galaxies through 3D modelling and visualisation"

- Authors: Tim Dykes (1), Claudio Gheller (2), B. S. Koribalski (3), K. Dolag (4) and Mel Krokos (5).
- Affiliations: (1) HPE HPC/AI EMEA Research Lab, Bristol, United Kingdom, (2) Institute of Radioastronomy, INAF, Via P. Gobetti, 101 40129 Bologna, Italy, (3) CSIRO Astronomy and Space Science, Australia Telescope National Facility, P.O. Box 76, Epping, NSW 2121, Australia, (4) Universitäts-Sternwarte München, Scheinerstr.1, D-81679 München, Germany, (5) School of Creative Technologies, University of Portsmouth, Eldon Building, Winstan Churchill Avenue, Portsmouth, United Kingdom.

Abstract

Observational astronomers survey the sky in great detail to gain a better understanding of many types of astronomical phenomena. In particular, the formation and evolution of galaxies, including our own, are a wide field of research. Three dimensional (spatial 3D) scientific visualisation is typically limited to simulated galaxies, due to the inherently two dimensional spatial resolution of Earth-based observations. However, with appropriate means of reconstruction, such visualisation can also be used to bring out the inherent 3D structure that exists in 2D observations of known galaxies, providing new views of these galaxies and visually illustrating the spatial relationships within galaxy groups that are not obvious in 2D. We present a novel approach to reconstruct and visualise 3D representations of nearby galaxies based on **observational data** using the scientific visualisation software **Spotch**. We apply our approach to a case study of the nearby **barred spiral galaxy** known as M83, presenting a new perspective of the M83 local group and highlighting the similarities between our reconstructed views of M83 and other known galaxies of similar inclinations.

Acknowledgement

KD acknowledges support by the ORIGINS cluster, funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy, EXC-2094, 390783311. MK acknowledges support by NEANIAS, funded by the EC Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 863448.

The article can be found in the journal *Astronomy and Computing*, **Volume 34**, January 2021, 100448 (DOI: 10.1016/j.ascom.2021.100448).

TAGS: [Space Research](#), [3D Modelling](#), [Scientific Visualisation](#)

Fig. 68 Scientific article on NEANIAS website

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

2.3.4. Whitepapers

NEANIAS project has produced and published 4 whitepapers that expose experiences, lessons learnt and best practices in several key areas of the project work, aimed at targeted interest groups in research, business and technology.

Work	Date
Best practices for interoperability and reuse	April 2021
Onboarding EOSC hub: best practices and lessons learnt	June 2021
Best practices for service onboarding the EOSC hub	August 2022
Best practices for sustainable services on EOSC	August 2022

Table 4 NEANIAS Whitepapers

All the whitepapers are available and downloadable from the NEANIAS website.

The screenshot shows the NEANIAS website interface. At the top left is the NEANIAS logo. To the right are navigation menus for PROJECT, EVENTS, PUBLICATIONS, and NEWS, along with a search bar. Below the navigation is a breadcrumb trail: Home / Publications / Scientific Publications / NEANIAS Whitepaper: Best practices for sustainable services on EOSC. The main content area features a sidebar on the left with icons for SPACE Services, ATMOSPHERE Services, UNDERWATER Services, and NEANIAS Open Event. The main text area is titled 'NEANIAS Whitepaper: Best practices for sustainable services on EOSC.' and contains the following text:

The whitepaper "Best practices for sustainable services on EOSC" has been produced by the NEANIAS project.

NEANIAS is an EU project that co-designs, develops and deliver innovative thematic services for European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) communities in three major sectors: Underwater research, Atmospheric research and Space research. NEANIAS aims to maximize the industry/research engagement by identifying and addressing all the challenges ensuring thus the sustainability of the services in question. These challenges are stemming not only from the funding needs but also from requirements of EOSC, the availability of data, the need for a common governance as well as from security and privacy related issues.

This white paper is based on the lessons learnt and the experiences gathered during the project. It describes the best practices for sustainable services on EOSC which could be a useful tool for all the stakeholders of the EOSC ecosystem.

• [Get the full document here.](#)

TAGS: [Innovation](#), [Business](#), [EOSC](#)

Fig. 69 NEANIAS Whitepaper on the website

2.3.5. Multimedia content

NEANIAS produced multimedia content, aimed at both the ecosystem (scientific community, researchers, developers, business, ...) and the general audience. In total, 40 videos have been created in the framework of NEANIAS project and all the content is published on NEANIAS YouTube Channel and communicated and promoted from the social networks.

Next table presents the videos created.

Video	Target
NEANIAS Project Overview	General audience
EOSC ARGOS Data Management Planning for NEANIAS Project.	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space services for the Astrophysics community.	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space servizi presentati al workshop GARR	Ecosystem

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NEANIAS Space presentation	General audience
NEANIAS Space. CAESAR: A next generation source finding service.	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space. Via Lactea Service	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space. Astra Data Navigator	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Underwater. Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data service presentation.	Ecosystem
NEANIAS 1st Open Call Video presentation	General audience
NEANIAS Underwater. Seafloor Mosaicking from Optical Data (MOS Service)	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Atmosphere. Atmo STRESS Service	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Atmosphere. Flux Density Services	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space. ADAM Platform	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Underwater. Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data service	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Atmosphere. Forecast service for computation of weather and air quality forecasts.	Ecosystem
Presentation of NEANIAS 2nd Open Call	Ecosystem
NEANIAS 2nd Open Call. Webinar	General audience
NEANIAS Space Astra Data Navigator Service webinar	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space. Latent Space Explorer	Ecosystem
Hack The Science 2022. Kick Off Event.	Ecosystem
Hack The Science 2022. Hack the Stellar Populations Challenge Introduction	Ecosystem
Hack The Science 2022. Hack The Planets Challenge Introduction	Ecosystem
Hack The Science 2022. Hack the UX of NEANIAS Challenge Introduction	Ecosystem
Hack The Science 2022. Hack and Explore the Latent Space Introduction	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Atmosphere. ATMO-4CAST service, enhanced version (new features)	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space. Latent Space Explorer Webinar	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space. Via Lactea Webinar.	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space. CAESAR ASTRO ML Webinar	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Core. Visualization Gateway webinar	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Space. ADAM webinar	Ecosystem
GEOInsight and NEANIAS services.	General audience
DDQ Pocket Science and NEANIAS services.	General audience
Walldone and NEANIAS services.	General audience
Relief Applications and NEANIAS services	General audience
NEANIAS Core. Distributed Deep Learning by Horovod	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Innovation and Assessment Workshop. Project Overview	General audience
NEANIAS Innovation and Assessment Workshop. Atmospheric Services	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Innovation and Assessment Workshop. Space services	Ecosystem
NEANIAS Innovation and Assessment Workshop. Underwater Services	Ecosystem

Fig. 70 Multimedia content published on NEANIAS channels

The videos consider all the specific fields of NEANIAS project (space research, atmospheric research, underwater research, core services) as well as general topics.

Next figure shows the typologies of their main content.

Fig. 71 Multimedia production for NEANIAS project by typology

2.4. Events and activities

NEANIAS project organized, participated, disseminated, was involved and interacted, both with the ecosystem and with the general public, through many activities, including fairs, congresses, conferences, workshops, webinars or hackathons. The consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic and the severe restrictions on mobility and the organization of face-to-face meetings had a full impact on the project, but it was effectively resolved by promoting online activity when it was needed. The participation in events was done by all the project partners, and it also meant a production of more than 60 conferences invited presentations, demos, papers and posters, providing a multidisciplinary view of the project purposes.

All the activities have been reported on NEANIAS website, considering the goals, the challenges, the work carried out and the results, and disseminated through the NEANIAS digital channels.

2.4.1. Conferences and workshops (co)organized or participated by NEANIAS

NEANIAS has had an intense activity in scientific dissemination, with transversal participation of all partners, being present in 74 events. In addition, NEANIAS members were in many other events as attendees, which provided the project members networking with the ecosystem and updates about the state-of-art. The vehicular language was mainly the English, although some national events were held in local languages.

Following, the most relevant workshops and conferences organised or co-organised by NEANIAS team, reported and disseminated through all NEANIAS digital channels during the project's life.

Event Name	Place & Date
NEANIAS Open Call Webinar	Online, 17/03/2021
Milano Digital Week	Milano & online, 18/03/2021
Blue Research and Innovation Days	Online, 19-23/04/2021
NEANIAS Underwater Services Webinar.	Online, 20/04/2021
International Workshop on 3D Rendering for Big Data.	Online, 28/04/2021
Underwater services: calibration tests workshop.	Aegina, 30/08/2021
Presentation of NEANIAS and its EOSC services to the Municipality and Port Authorities of the island city of Aegina.	Aegina, 30/09/2021

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NEANIAS Underwater services organized a CNRS Workshop.	Aigina, 30/10/2021
2nd Open Call webinar	Online, 4/11/2021
Workshop on 2nd release of services U2, U3.	Aix-Marseille University, 19/11/2021
Presentation of the results of the 2 nd release of the NEANIAS Services during the MAGS Conference	Aix-Marseille University, 25-26/11/2021
ARGOS-OpenDMP	Athens, 3/03/2022
Raise Your Voice Towards Sustainability workshop	Aveiro, 15/03/2022
NEANIAS Space: Astra Data Navigator Service	Online, 27/04/2022
Roteiro da Sustentabilidade: Inteligência e Inovação no Ambiente Urbano".	Aveiro, 28/04/2022
ATMO4CAST service presented at the University of Aveiro.	Aveiro, 19/05/2022
Workshop to present its Atmospheric thematic services.	Xanthi, 3/06/2022
NEANIAS Space. Latent Space Explorer Webinar	Online, 7/06/2022
NEANIAS Space. ViaLactea Webinar.	Online, 8/06/2022
NEANIAS SPACE CAESAR & AstroML Webinar.	Online, 15/06/2022
Visualization gateway webinar	Online, 22/07/2022
NEANIAS SPACE ADAM-Explorer: Accessing science-ready Mars surface images.	Online, 27/04/2022
Hack the Science 2022 Webinar	Milano & Online, 5/05/2022
Atmospheric Workshop	Online & Athens, 29/06/2022
Presentation of NEANIAS and its EOSC services	Aegina, 9/07/2022
NEANIAS Open Innovation Workshop	Online & Athens, 5/09/2022
86th Thessaloniki International Fair	Thessaloniki, 10-18/9/2022
NEANIAS Open Event	Online & Barcelona, 22-23/09/2022
NEANIAS interactive Workshop in the framework of the '1st International Conference of Mediterranean Harbour and Coastal Archaeology 2022'	Aix-Marseille University & online, 27/09/2022
IPR Workshop	Online, 20/10/2022
Innovation & Assessment Workshop	Athens Online, 26/10/2022

Table 5 Workshops and conferences (co)organised by NEANIAS

Next figure illustrates the participation in the Innovation and assessment workshop, organized by NEANIAS project.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 72 Workshops and conferences (co)organised by NEANIAS (sample)

Next figure illustrates the presentation of NEANIAS project and its EO/SC services to stakeholders from the Municipality and Port Authorities of the island city of Aegina (30-09-2021), where scientific research is conducted by the NEANIAS team members and underwater databases are tested on the NEANIAS services.

Fig. 73 Workshops and conferences (co)organised by NEANIAS (sample)@L. Roux (CCJ-CNRS-AMU)

And next the workshop at Aix-Marseille University on 19th November 2021 to test the 2nd release of Services U2 and U3.

Fig. 74 Workshops and conferences (co)organised by NEANIAS (sample) @Ph. Soubias (CCI-CNRS-AMU)

Next, the NEANIAS Workshop in the framework of the ‘1st International Conference of Mediterranean Harbour and Coastal Archaeology 2022’ (Aix-Marseille University and online (27/09/2022)). During the Conference, all participants, **including scientists from underwater archaeology, marine geology and geomorphology, geoinformatics, etc, as well as stakeholders from all around the Mediterranean counties**, had the opportunity to test interactively three Innovative Underwater Services (Bathymetry mapping, Seafloor mosaicking and Seabed Classification) now developed for the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) **in the framework of a NEANIAS workshop that was organised specifically in this event.**

Fig. 75 Workshops and conferences (co)organised by NEANIAS (sample) @Ph.Soubias (CCI-CNRS-AMU)

Following, the most relevant workshops and conferences participated by NEANIAS team, reported and disseminated through all NEANIAS digital channels during the project’s life.

Event Name	Place & Date
European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO)	Athens, 12-14/02/2020
Toward the Big Data Analysis: Visual Analytic, Machine Learning and future perspectives Webinar	Online, 22/04/2020

 Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

6th International Conference GISTAM-2020	Online, 7-9/05/2020
IoTBDs-2020 (5th International Conference on Internet of Things, Big Data and Security)	Prague & online, 9/05/2020
SACI 2020 IEEE 14th International Symposium on Applied Computational Intelligence and Informatics	Timișoara, Romania, 21-23/05/2020
European Astronomical Society Annual Meeting	Online, 29/06/2020 - 3/07/2020
InnoWorld 2020	Online, 04/07/2020
Computing Conference 2020	Online, 16/07/2020
EOSC Landscape Final Validation Workshop	Brussels & online. 28-29/09/2020
2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop "Research Infrastructures shaping EOSC"	Online, 06-07/10/2020
GARR-2020 Workshop	Online, 2-6/11/2020
XXX Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems (ADASS) Conference	Granada & online, 8-12/11/2020
Research Data Alliance 2020	Online, 9-12/11/2020
e-Infrastructures Reflection Group workshop	Online, 1-2/12/2020
Budapest Science Meetup	Online, 10/12/2020
Software and Cyberinfrastructure for Astronomy VI	Online, 14-18/12/2020
Risk, Disaster and Crisis Management with the Use of Modern Technologies at National and International Level	Online, 14/02/2021
Artificial Intelligence for big satellite data	Online, 25/02/2021
SKA Conference 2021	Online, 15-19/03/2021
2nd International Conference Dive in Blue Growth on the Promotion of Accessible Underwater Cultural Heritage Sites.	Online, 13/05/2021.
Virtual conference on Applications of Statistical Methods and Machine Learning	Online, 17-21/05/2021
INODE EOSC Workshop	Online, 21/05/2021.
EOSC Symposium 2021	Online, 15-18/06/2021
5th Planetary Data Workshop	Online, 1/07/2021
Cidades Resilientes Festival	Coimbra, 16/07/2021.
EOSC portal onboarding & IVOA Registry resource publishing" workshop.	Online, 28/09/2021.
3rd National Workshop on the SKA Project - The Italian Route to the SKAO Revolution.	Online, 4-8/10/2021.
Thessaloniki Climathon 2021	Thessaloniki, 13-14/11/2021.
Maritime Archaeology Graduate Symposium 2021.	Aix-Marseille University, 25-26/11/2021.
EOSC Enhance webinar	Online, 25/11/2021.
UMCidades: Desafios Tecnológicos das Cidades	Braga, 26/11/2021.
International Conference on Smart, Sustainable, Social and Accessible Tourism (SSAT 2021).	Aveiro, 26/11/2021.
20th International Conference of the Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence (AixIA-2021)	Online, 1/12/2021
NEANIAS Underwater presented at the UNESCO headquarters.	Paris, 12/12/2021

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NEANIAS Underwater. An Accessible Ocean Workshop	Online, May 10-12, 2022.
35th Nordic Geological Winter Meeting 2022	Reykjavík, 11-13/05/2022.
GeoHub 2022	Venice & Online, 19/05/2022.
NEANIAS Underwater presented at UNESCO Unitwin network	22/05/2022.
EGU General Assembly 2022	23/05/2022.
International Conference on Machine Learning for Astrophysics (ML4ASTRO)	Catania & online, 30/05-1/06/2022.
Cities on Volcanoes 11, Heraklison, Crete	12/06/2022
TNC 2022	Trieste & Online, 13-17/06/2022.
GeoPython 2022	20/06/2022
European Astronomical Society Annual Meeting 2022.	Valencia & Online, 27/6 – 1/07, 2022.
26th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries	Padua, 20/09/2022
Open Aire Week 2022. Climate Justice	Online, 25/10/2022

Table 6 Workshops and conferences supported by NEANIAS

Next figure illustrates the participation in the 20th International Conference of the Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence (AIxIA-2021).

Fig. 76 Participation in a workshop (sample)

2.4.2. Fairs and exhibitions participated

NEANIAS participated in different scientific and commercial fairs and exhibitions, to publicize and promote the services developed in the scope of the project to future users, collaborators, researchers, developers, prescribers or investors, as well as to a general public.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Next table presents the main fairs and exhibitions participated by NEANIAS.

Event Name	Place & Date
European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO)	Athens, 12-14/02/2020
European Astronomical Society Annual Meeting	Online, 29/06/2020 - 3/07/2020
EOSC Project Expo	Online, 16-19/11/2020
Milano Digital Week	Milano & online, 18/03/2021
Cidades Resilientes Festival	Coimbra, 16/07/2021.
85th Thessaloniki International Fair	Thessaloniki, 11-19/09/2021.
Open Science Fair 2021.	Online, 22-23/09/2021.
Smart City Expo World Congress.	Barcelona, 15-17/11/2021
Portugal Smart Cities Summit	Lisboa, 16-18/11/2021.
Patras Innovation Quest 2021	Online, 4-6/12/2021.
XXV Congresso da Associação de Municípios Portugueses (ANMP).	Aveiro, 11-12/12/2021.
Green Project Expo	Online, 25/01/2022.
Mobile World Congress 2022.	Barcelona, 28/02 -8/03, 2022.
4YFN Congress.	Barcelona, 28/02-3/03, 2022.
Roteiro da Sustentabilidade: Inteligência e Inovação no Ambiente Urbano".	Aveiro, 28/04/2022.
35th Nordic Geological Winter Meeting 2022	Reykjavík, 11-13/05/2022.
GeoHub 2022	Venice & Online, 19/05/2022.
Living Planet Symposium 2022	Bonn, 23-27/05/2022.
Hannover Messe	Hannover, 30/05/2022 to 02/06/2022.
European Astronomical Society Annual Meeting 2022.	Valencia & Online, 27/6 – 1/07, 2022.
86th Thessaloniki International Fair	Thessaloniki, 10-18/9/2022
1st International Conference of Mediterranean Harbour and Coastal Archaeology 2022	Aix-en-Provence & online, 27/09/2022

Next figure illustrates the participation in a scientific exhibition, where we can see the NEANIAS project manager and the scientific coordinator.

Fig. 77 Fairs and exhibitions participated by NEANIAS (sample)

Next, the main commercial and exploitation events participated by NEANIAS.

Event Name	Place & Date
EOSC Project Expo	Online, 16-19/11/2020
Milano Digital Week	Milano & online, 18/03/2021
Cidades Resilientes Festival	Coimbra, 16/07/2021.
85th Thessaloniki International Fair	Thessaloniki, 11- 19/09/2021.
Smart City Expo World Congress.	Barcelona, 15-17/11/2021
Portugal Smart Cities Summit	Lisboa, 16-18/11/2021.
Patras Innovation Quest 2021	Online, 4-6/12/2021.
XXV Congresso da Associação de Municípios Portugueses (ANMP).	Aveiro, 11-12/12/2021.
Mobile World Congress 2022.	Barcelona, 28/02 -8/03, 2022.
Roteiro da Sustentabilidade: Inteligência e Inovação no Ambiente Urbano".	Aveiro, 28/04/2022.
35th Nordic Geological Winter Meeting 2022	Reykjavík, 11-13/05/2022.
GeoHub 2022	Venice & Online, 19/05/2022.
Living Planet Symposium 2022	Bonn, 23-27/05/2022.
Hannover Messe	Hannover, 30/05/2022 to 02/06/2022.
TNC 2022	Trieste & Online, 13- 17/06/2022.
86th Thessaloniki International Fair	Thessaloniki, 10-18/9/2022
1st International Conference of Mediterranean Harbour and Coastal Archaeology 2022	Marseille & online, 27/09/2022

Table 7 Commercial and exploitation events participated by NEANIAS

Next figure illustrates the participation of NEANIAS in a commercial exhibition.

Fig. 78 Participation in commercial exhibition

The participation in the EOSC Project Expo should be highlighted. NEANIAS actively participated at EOSC Projects EXPO - Realising the European Open Science Cloud Conference. Organized as part of the Realising the European Open Science Cloud joint event by the EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC projects.

The EOSC Projects EXPO was the first virtual exhibition showcasing initiatives and projects of the European Open Science Cloud. NEANIAS representatives attended the booth during the exhibition days, and we chatted with the more than 30 projects that participated with us, as well as with the visitors to the event. Some synergies with other projects have been identified and a productive collaboration may be realized in near future.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 79 NEANIAS booth at EOSC Project Expo

The event was very fruitful for NEANIAS. The exhibition provided us with many opportunities to present the challenges of NEANIAS and our services, both to the general and thematic public. We also had the opportunity to participate in the EOSC framework, to interact with the innovation ecosystem, make business contacts with potential stakeholders, stay updated through many interesting conferences and last, but not least, to promote open science initiatives and research infrastructures liaison with other projects.

And last, but not least, NEANIAS was awarded for the best booth as a result of a contest carried out among the attendants, participants and the organization of the exhibition.

Fig. 80 NEANIAS awarded at EOSC Project Expo

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

NEANIAS booth featured banners, downloadable material (executive presentations and brochures), multimedia content, links to our website and connections to our digital channels. We are pleased to think that NEANIAS messages are clearly reaching our stakeholders as an important task of our dissemination, collaboration, outreach and engagement activities, making NEANIAS well known and appreciated by the ecosystem.

Fig. 81 Acknowledgments from EOSC ecosystem to NEANIAS project

All the events were presented on the NEANIAS website.

2.4.3. Hackathons and Datathons

Below are the most relevant hackathons and datathons in which NEANIAS participated, contributing knowledge, resources, experiences and promoting, disseminating and attracting participants and attendees from all NEANIAS channels.

NEANIAS (co)organized 4 datathons and hackathons:

Event Name	Place & Date	Participants
Copernicus Hackathon 2020	Athens & online, 8/5 - 5/6 2020	50
Blue Research and Innovation Days Hackathon	Online, 21-23/04 2021	30
ATMO-stress Geo Datathon	Milano Bicocca & Online, March 25, 2022.	25
Hack the Science 2022	Milano Bicocca & Online, May 5 - June 2, 2022.	30

Table 8 Datathons and hackathons (co)organized by NEANIAS

Also, NEANIAS supported 4 datathons and hackathons:

Event Name	Place & Date	Participants
Copernicus Hackathon 2019	Athens, 8-9/11 2019	50
Thessaloniki Climathon 2021	Thessaloniki, 13-14/11/2021.	55
Sustainability Hackathon	Athens, 15-17/04/2022.	120

Table 9 Datathons and hackathons supported by NEANIAS

2.4.3.1. Datathons and hackathons (co)organized by NEANIAS

NEANIAS project organized / co-organized 4 datathons and hackathons regarding NEANIAS topics and challenges.

2.4.3.1.1. Copernicus Hackathon 2020

The Copernicus Hackathon in Athens was organised by Corallia, the innovation unit of the Athena Research and Innovation Centre in Information Communication & Knowledge Technologies, with the support of NEANIAS Project. 15 teams participated in this event that was held online from Friday, May 8, 2020, 2:00 PM to - Friday, June 5, 2020.

Fig. 82 Copernicus Hackathon in Athens, 2020

Fig. 83 NEANIAS presentation at Copernicus Hackathon 2020

On Friday 19.6.2020, at ATHENA RC premises, NEANIAS project representatives, welcomed representatives of winning teams of the Athens CopHackOn 2020. NEANIAS project representatives, Eleni Petra, PM, Prof. Konstantinos Karantzalos Steering Committee Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Evi Nomikou, WP2 leader, Prof. Spyros Rapsomanikis, WP3 Leader (remotely), Dr. George Papastefanatos, WP8 leader and Mr. Panos Spyrou from Corallia (remotely) welcomed representatives of the two winning teams of the Athens CopHackOn 2020 and had the opportunity to discuss about the teams' applications as well as their future plans and get their award, a laptop PC and NEANIAS souvenirs.

Fig. 84 Copernicus Hackathon 2020, awards

2.4.3.1.2. *Blue Research and innovation days' hackathon*

The main objective of Blue Research and Innovation Days was to present ongoing cutting-edge projects along with a specially-shaped hackathon towards bringing together consortia, the scientific community and industry working at the core of the 'blue economy' by promoting synergies as well as shaping common future activities. The event gave the opportunity in every

project to present its particular objectives, the current results, its cloud services, Open and Big Data research and results, the possible business cases providing by this way the possibility to the participants to investigate common approaches to specific problems, complementarities, synergies perspectives, future collaborations.

All blue economy (marine, fisheries, underwater) enthusiasts: data scientists and practitioners, students, researchers, representatives from both private and public sector, that work to improve the fisheries, marine, underwater and environmental management with applications in energy, geohazards management, underwater archaeology, or develop ICT solutions for marine, underwater monitoring were invited to join the hackathon co-organized by the NEANIAS, I4Sea and INFORE projects from April 21 to 23, 2021, online. The event was kindly supported by ATHENA RC.

Eleni Petra represented NEANIAS as member of the Blue Research and Innovation Days Hackathon Programme committee, and Evi Nomikou (WP2 Leader), Kalliopi Baika, Danaï Lampridou, Valsamis, and Makis Ntouskos were the NEANIAS representatives in the Blue Research and Innovation Days Hackathon Scientific Committee.

Fig. 85 Blue Research and innovation Week.

The hackathon at the end of the week integrated challenges from three specific projects towards providing the participants access to real world scenarios, business cases and open issues. Thus, it promoted the design and development of new approaches and novel solutions related to various Blue Economy aspects. The hackathon started on 21st of April, during the Blue Research Innovation Days and completed at the end of same week. Challenges were integrated from three specific projects, NEANIAS, i4sea and INFORE providing the participants access to real world scenarios, business cases and open issues.

7 Teams and 26 participants took part in the Hackathon where 5 teams ended presenting their work.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 86 Hackathon awards and NEANIAS

2.4.3.1.3. *Geo Datathon on NEANIAS Atmospheric Services*

The Geo Datathon was held on March 28, 2022, by Università Degli Studi di Milano Bicocca. It was focused on introducing the NEANIAS ATMO-STRESS service to students in a specific geology event at the university.

The ATMO-STRESS service, developed in the framework of the NEANIAS project, fills the geological community need of the implementation of a service capable of calculating and visualize the stress trajectories in plan and 3D view correlating the distance of the earthquake epicentre and hypocentre location from the crater, the tectonic stress characteristics (fault kinematics trajectories of the principal stresses obtainable from the earthquake focal mechanism solution), and the magnitude of the seismic event.

Fig. 87 Geo Datathon on NEANIAS Atmospheric Services

25 students participated in the event, experiencing the NEANIAS EOSC services and providing interesting feed-back to the project team. One of the most common feed-back was that the service is very easy to learn and use. Next release will be focused on the improving of the computing capacity.

2.4.3.1.4. *Hack the Science 2022*

This event was a hackathon about science, scientific computing, user experience, cloud computing, organized by the NEANIAS H2020 project in Milano & Online, from May 5, 2022 to July 28, 2022.

Fig. 88 NEANIAS Hack the Science 2020 image

The participants had to deal with challenges were related to NEANIAS challenges: (1) Hack the stellar populations, (2) Hack the planets or (3) Hack the UX of NEANIAS.

The winner of HACK THE SCIENCE 2022 is the OASBO Team. The team worked in the challenge of labelling Martian surface images according to their texture to support further analysis regarding the planet morphology using NEANIAS SPACE Services. In particular the ADAM-Space service was very useful to retrieve the dataset. For its achievement, they had to deal with Image processing, Artificial intelligence or Terrain morphology characterisation.

Fig. 89 NEANIAS Hack the Science 2020 winner

2.4.3.2. Datathons and hackathons supported by NEANIAS

NEANIAS project actively supported 4 datathons and hackathons that included objectives, challenges and technologies related to the project.

2.4.3.2.1. Copernicus Hackathon in Athens, 2019

NEANIAS team participated in Copernicus Hackathon on 8-9/11/2019 in Athens, presenting relative challenge regarding air quality monitoring and forecasting in tourism. The Copernicus Hackathon, part of the European Union Copernicus Start-up Programme, is set to facilitate the co-creation of disruptive and breakthrough solutions, new business ideas and opportunities based on Copernicus data and services in Athens, Greece.

The Copernicus Hackathon in Athens is organized by the innovation unit of the Athena Research and Innovation Center in Information Communication & Knowledge Technologies, in collaboration with the Greek Space Technologies and Applications Cluster (si-Cluster), the Hellenic Association of Space Industries (HASI), Space Innovation (SPIN), the project i4Sea, and the Greek Copernicus Relay Network and the Greek Copernicus Academy Network.

Fig. 90 Copernicus Hackathon in Athens, 2019

2.4.3.2.2. Thessaloniki Climathon 2021

NEANIAS supported the Thessaloniki Climathon 2021. This year, the challenge presented was "Urban Energy Transition". At its heart is the need to reduce energy-related CO2 emissions to limit climate change.

Fig. 91 Thessaloniki Climathon 2021

The event was organized by EIT Climate-KIC, a Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC), working to accelerate the transition to a zero-carbon, climate-resilient society. Supported by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology, it identifies and supports innovation that helps society mitigate and adapt to climate change. EIT Climate-KIC believes that a decarbonised, sustainable economy is not only necessary to prevent catastrophic climate change but presents a wealth of opportunities for business and society.

EIT Climate-KIC brings together partners in the worlds of business, academia, and the public and non-profit sectors to create networks of expertise, through which innovative products, services and systems can be developed, brought to market and scaled-up for impact. Climathon is a city-based programme that offers a clear pathway to action and interaction – an opportunity for cities and citizens to co-create local ideas to shared climate challenges. Climathon brings together students, young and older people, organizations, local stakeholders, the public and private sector, the local authorities in order to tackle a local challenge.

Fig. 92 Thessaloniki Climathon 2021

NEANIAS services and the project itself are very aligned with the challenges presented. NEANIAS supported EIT Climate-KIC through dedicated presentations, the technical expertise of the team, and mentoring.

2.4.3.2.3. *Sustainability Hackathon*

NEANIAS had a fruitful experience participating in Innovathens with the A1 service among 29 teams. The Sustainability Hackathon was the second open innovation action aimed at community and business activation to create innovative applications that contribute through technology and digitization to the goals of sustainability, education and entrepreneurship. The event took place on April 15-16-17, hybrid, physical at Innovathens (100 Pireaus str., Gkazi) and remotely with digital tools! Applications.

Fig. 93 Sustainability Hackathon

The Sustainability Hackathon had the following main objectives:

- Creating a culture of innovation and collaborations within the organization.
- Supporting youth and innovative entrepreneurship, opportunities for young people, combating unemployment.
- Support to the local economy, as competitors from all over Greece will be able to participate, who can then set up their own business.
- Highlighting smart and innovative solutions to the problems and challenges that concern both the themes of the campaign and the citizens who deal with related issues.
- Improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the campaign, utilizing new emerging technologies.
- Connecting the campaign with the technological innovation and entrepreneurship community of our country.
- Creating an ecosystem of innovation and entrepreneurship in the field of sustainability.

Fig. 94 Sustainability Hackathon

2.4.3.2.4. *CASSINI Hackathon*

NEANIAS team supported the CASSINI Hackathon Greece. The event had 50 participants from many countries in Europe. The hackathon in Greece was organised by Corallia, as part of the Athena Research Center. As an incubator, youth entrepreneurship accelerator and multi-cluster facilitator, Corallia has a vision to develop an environment with the right conditions to help sciences, innovation, and entrepreneurship flourish in Greece.

Fig. 95 CASSINI Hackathon

The CASSINI Hackathon Greece took place at Corallia's offices: Monumental Plaza, Building C, Kifissias Ave. 44, GR-15125 Maroussi, Athens. The teams were able to participate physically (on-site) or virtually (from home). NEANIAS team was represented by its Project Manager, Eleni Petra, who participated as a mentor.

Fig. 96 CASSINI Hackathon

2.4.4. NEANIAS Open Calls

The WP10 also worked actively in the organization, promotion, attraction of applicants and dissemination of the results of the Open Calls of the project. The details are presented in WP5's deliverables. The Open Calls also represented commercial exploitation event for the three thematic sectors of NEANIAS, as well as for the core IT technologies.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Event Name	Place & Date	Participants
NEANIAS 1st Open Call	Online, started on 08/04/2021	21
NEANIAS 2nd Open Call	Online, started 11/10/2021	6

Table 10 Open Calls

The purpose of NEANIAS Open Calls is to spark and support the development of a wide variety of innovation projects by providing novel services created in the frame of the NEANIAS project, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations and contributing to advance research and innovation in Europe. The overarching goal was to build up and strengthen the European innovation community by identifying and supporting innovative projects with novel services developed in the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research fields. Innovation in this scope may refer to (a) new operation models for existing services, that can exploit NEANIAS resources (b) improving existing services utilizing NEANIAS offerings to increase their overall offering (c) brand new services inspired by NEANIAS offerings (d) new services in need offerings such as NEANIAS and EOOSC ones, and many more.

To boost the development of new business opportunities and accelerate the onboarding of external users into the project, NEANIAS organized its first Open Call for Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Science initiatives.

The first Open Call was launched on February 8, 2021 and was closed on April 9, 2021.

Fig. 97 NEANIAS 1st Open dedicated Call banner

After the successful 1st NEANIAS Open Call, NEANIAS launched the 2nd Open Call and invited further SME-s, start-ups, to submit a proposal to receive professional expert support, validate innovative ideas and boost the development with NEANIAS services and experts. The call opening date was on October 11, 2021, and the deadline of submission was on December 8, 2021. The duration of participation was 3-6 Months.

Fig. 98 NEANIAS 2nd Open dedicated Call banner

For both calls, NEANIAS team organized a webinar to promote, engage and attract the users, and produced a dedicated video to present them.

2.4.5. NEANIAS Open Event

The NEANIAS Open Event was planned for the last quarter of the project to present the objectives of the project, its motivations, the challenges undertaken, the results obtained and the innovative digital solutions available on the EOSC platform, offering a practical knowledge of NEANIAS from all perspectives (technological, functional, commercial, strategic), as well as the access to the project team.

Fig. 99 NEANIAS Open Event design

The event was aimed both to NEANIAS stakeholders and general audience. It was organized from the WP 10 “Communication, Dissemination and Outreach”, led by RICOH and had the support of the NEANIAS partners.

The deliverable D10.5 “NEANIAS Open Event” reports on the activities and results in the context of the organization of the NEANIAS Open Event, carried on September 22nd and 23rd, 2022, in Sant Cugat del Vallès (Barcelona, Spain). The document presents the work carried out considering throughout the process: the initial planning, including the strategic and organizational aspects, the details of the event developed, the results and impacts and finally a general description of the management and coordination model.

Fig. 100 NEANIAS Open Event picture

The event reached both to NEANIAS stakeholders and general audience. The participation of the NEANIAS partners (many of them in person) allowed us to present the full scope of the NEANIAS project (Underwater, Space, Atmospheric and Core services) from all its perspectives - strategic, functional, business, commercial, technological, innovation, user needs, EOSC and the European framework – as well as to engage potential users and to promote their onboarding.

2.4.6. Meetings

NEANIAS intended to have attended and participated in numerous conferences and fairs to present the project, enrich networking, identify new business models and opportunities, and establish connections with the ecosystem, as well as identify new trends and technological opportunities in the project's application areas. Sadly, several events were cancelled due to the coronavirus outbreak, especially those of a more transversal, multidisciplinary and multitudinous type. Others moved to virtual.

Nevertheless, the NEANIAS team held many e-meetings with relevant stakeholders, presenting NEANIAS and discussing innovation, business and the challenges of new cloud services to keep up-to-date and enrich the knowledge about the scope of the project, being the NEANIAS digital channels a fruitful point of contact.

Regarding the ecosystem, contact has been maintained from thematic sectors, promoting professional contacts and the opportunities offered by participation in congresses and conferences.

In addition, the participation of NEANIAS members in European working groups gave us the chance to achieve new networking with relevant players. It is worth noting that Eleni Petra, Project Manager and Georgios Kakaletis, Technical Manager of NEANIAS project, became members of the EOSC Training and Skills Working Group and the Architecture Working Group respectively.

2.5. Open Science initiatives and Research Infrastructures liaison activities

As NEANIAS seeks to maximise its impact and optimise the use of resources, an essential part is the establishment of liaison activities with initiatives, taskforces or projects that operate in the areas of Open Science, the EOSC and Research Infrastructures (including ESFRI and EOSC Hub satellite projects).

The task meant seek, locate and establish the links with those initiatives, according to the plan, and monitor the result of those activities and report back to all project structures the progress and results of those activities.

2.5.1. Projects & initiatives liaised with, from the same call, sharing experiences and solutions to challenges.

NEANIAS has collaborated closely with three projects and initiatives of the same H2020 call, sharing knowledge, experiences and activities (including the common organization of events and dissemination activities) by identifying and enhancing synergies of their developments to shared challenges.

Fig. 101 Projects from the same Call, liaised with NEANIAS

2.5.1.1. Cos4Cloud Project

<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu>

Cos4Cloud project aims to facilitate open science and citizen science initiatives by designing and implementing services. The project will design and prototype these new services using deep machine learning, automatic video recognition, and other cutting-edge technologies.

2.5.1.2. TRIPLE Project

<https://www.gotriple.eu>

TRIPLE Project was launched on 7 October 2019. It will be one of the dedicated services of OPERAS, the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area.

Based on the Isidore search engine developed by the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), the TRIPLE platform will provide a single access point for users (researchers, institutions such as universities and libraries, but also enterprises, consultancies, media and service providers):

- to discover and reuse open scholarly SSH resources, i.e. research data and publications, which are currently scattered across local repositories;
- to find and connect with other researchers and projects across disciplinary and language boundaries
- to make use of innovative tools to support research (e.g., visualisation, annotation, trust building and recommender system);
- to discover new ways of funding research (e.g., crowdfunding).

2.5.1.3. INODE Project

<http://www.inode-project.eu>

INODE (Intelligent Open Data Exploration), a classic unified, comprehensive platform that provides extensive access to open datasets through natural language queries in the fields of Cancer Biomarker Research, Research and Innovation Policy Making and Astrophysics, for a wide range of users from larger scientific communities to public.

2.5.2. Other relevant H2020 projects & research infrastructures liaised with NEANIAS

In addition, there are more H2020 projects, research infrastructures and relevant programs liaised with NEANIAS, sharing experience and exploiting synergies. NEANIAS is continuously linked with these projects and initiatives, being aware of prospective projects and the activities that we promote, disseminate and participate in, mainly those related to Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research, as well as the information technologies that allow the development of NEANIAS services.

Fig. 102 Relevant H2020 projects & research infrastructures liaised with NEANIAS

2.5.2.1. OPENAIRE (RI)

www.openaire.eu/openaire-project

OPENAIRE aims to shift scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research by means of Align policies, Provide open science services, Link research, Monitor (open) science, Train for open science, Build global bridges and Facilitate Open Innovation.

2.5.2.2. RDA

<https://grants.rd-alliance.org/>

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) is an international member-based organisation focused on the development of infrastructure and community activities to reduce the social and technical barriers to data sharing and re-use and to promote the acceleration of data driven innovation and discovery worldwide. RDA Europe 4.0 is an offshoot of the international Research Data Alliance (RDA) and a Coordination & Support Action co-funded by the European Commission under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Horizon 2020 (H2020). The objective of RDA Europe 4.0 is to become the centrepiece for an EU Open Science Strategy, bringing forward an RDA legacy in Europe, providing skilled, voluntary resources from the EU investment to address Digital Single Market issues. In order to reach this objective, between 2018 and 2020 RDA Europe 4.0 supported growing the community of research data experts

and practitioners by a series of open calls offering grants for new RDA Europe national nodes, early career researchers and experts, RDA ambassadors, and RDA output-adoption.

2.5.2.3. CATRIS

<https://project.catris.eu/>

CatRIS is an open, trusted and user-friendly portal to a harmonised and aggregated catalogue of services and resources provided by Research Infrastructures (RI) and Core Facilities (CF) across Europe. It is a bottom-up initiative that is meant to be populated and run by RI and CF service providers at European, national, regional and institutional levels. CatRIS will be complementary to and interoperable with the EOSC catalogue.

2.5.2.4. EMSO-ERIC

<http://emso.eu/>

The European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO) aims to explore the oceans, to gain a better understanding of phenomena happening within and below them, and to explain the critical role that these phenomena play in the broader Earth systems. EMSO consists in a system of regional facilities placed at key sites around Europe, from North East to the Atlantic, through the Mediterranean, to the Black Sea. Observatories are platforms equipped with multiple sensors, placed along the water column and on the seafloor. They constantly measure different biogeochemical and physical parameters, that address natural hazards, climate change and marine ecosystems.

EMSO offers data and services to a large and diverse group of users, from scientists and industries to institutions and policy makers. It is an extraordinary infrastructure to provide relevant information for defining environmental policies based on scientific data. EMSO is a consortium of partners sharing in a common strategic framework scientific facility (data, instruments, computing and storage capacity). Formally it is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), legal framework created for pan-European large-scale research infrastructures.

2.5.2.5. EOSC Enhance

<https://eosc-portal.eu/enhance>

As a trusted virtual environment enabling the data-driven, cross-disciplinary Open Science which holds the key to advances in research and innovation, the EOSC will offer some 1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science, technology, and the humanities and social sciences a single access point to data services spanning the full data life cycle. This will be achieved by federating existing research infrastructures currently dispersed across disciplines and states.

During the lifetime of EOSC Enhance, project partners develop and improve the functionality of the EOSC Portal, further augmenting the catalogue of services assembled to date, and connecting independent, thematic data clouds for the benefit of users and service providers across Europe.

2.5.2.6. ESCAPE (RI)

<https://projectescape.eu/>

ESCAPE (European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures) brings together the astronomy, astroparticle and particle physics communities. With this, ESCAPE puts together a cluster with ESFRI projects with aligned challenges of data-driven research, with demonstrated capabilities in addressing various stages of data workflow and concerned with fundamental research through complementary approaches.

2.5.2.7. Blue-Cloud

<https://www.blue-cloud.org/>

Blue-Cloud is a European H2020 project with the overarching aim of federating and piloting innovative services for Marine Research and the Blue Economy. The project is working towards the establishment of a marine-thematic EOSC serving the Blue Economy, Marine Environment and Marine Knowledge agendas. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) aims to provide a virtual environment with open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines.

There is a collaboration agreement in specific topics: Dissemination activities together – exchange of logos/website updates regarding projects collaboration/social media, discussed about common strategies.

2.5.2.8. MASTER

<http://www.master-project-h2020.eu/>

MASTER (Multiple ASpects Trajectory management and analysis) is a project funded under the call H2020-MSCA-RISE-2017 with the objective of forming an international and inter-sectoral network of organisations working on a joint research programme to define new methods to build, manage and analyse multiple aspects semantic trajectories.

2.5.2.9. Ni4Os

<https://ni4os.eu/>

National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe – NI4OS Europe, aims to be a core contributor to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) service portfolio, commit to EOSC governance and ensure inclusiveness on the European level for enabling global Open Science.

The project presents the following lines of action: (i) Support the development and inclusion of the national Open Science Cloud initiatives in 15 Member States and Associated Countries in the EOSC governance; (ii) Instill within the community the EOSC philosophy and FAIR principles for data Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability; (iii) Provide technical and policy support for on-boarding of service providers into EOSC, including generic services (compute, data storage, data management), thematic services, repositories and data sets.

2.5.2.10. ECOGAL

<http://www.ecogal.eu/>

The project aims to understanding the Galactic ecosystem, from the disk of the Milky Way to the formation sites of stars and planets. It is based on a unique combination of theoretical modelling and multi-wavelengths observations, three fundamental issues: planets, galaxies and stars.

2.5.2.11. RAMONES

<https://ramones-project.eu/>

The project aims to design, develop and validate (i) for the first time, a broad set of novel instruments for measuring radioactivity in seabed and water column; (ii) novel adaptation, self-deployment and self-awareness collaborative marine robotics capabilities for the efficient operation and sensing with the new marine radiometry instrumentation and (iii) novel statistical, artificial intelligence and environmental modelling methodologies for processing and modelling marine radioactivity multi-modal data.

2.5.2.12. VesselAI

<https://vessel-ai.eu/>

VesselAI aims at realising a holistic, beyond the state-of-the-art AI-empowered framework for decision-support models, data analytics and visualisations to build digital twins and maritime applications for a diverse set of cases with high impact, including simulating and predicting vessel behaviour and manoeuvring (including the human factor), ship energy design optimisation, autonomous shipping and fleet intelligence.

2.5.2.13. EIT Climate-KIC

<https://www.climate-kic.org/>

EIT Climate-KIC is a Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC), working to accelerate the transition to a zero-carbon, climate-resilient society. Supported by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology, we identify and support innovation that helps society mitigate and adapt to climate change. We believe that a decarbonised, sustainable economy is not only necessary to prevent catastrophic climate change, but presents a wealth of opportunities for business and society. They bring together partners in the worlds of business, academia, and the public and non-profit sectors to create networks of expertise, through which innovative products, services and systems can be developed, brought to market and scaled-up for impact. EIT Climate-KIC brings together the most effective groups to create the innovation that can lead to systemic change.

2.5.2.14. INFORE

<https://www.infore-project.eu/>

The aim of the INFORE project is to address the challenges posed by huge datasets and pave the way for real-time, interactive extreme-scale analytics and forecasting. The ability to forecast, as early as possible, a good approximation to the outcome of a time-consuming and resource demanding computational task allows to quickly identify undesired outcomes and save valuable amount of time, effort and computational resources.

2.5.2.15. I-BIDaaS

<https://www.ibidaas.eu/concept/>

I-BiDaaS is a self-service solution, aiming to empower users to easily utilize and interact with big data technologies by designing, building and demonstrating a unified framework that significantly increases the speed of data analysis while coping with the rate of data asset growth and facilitates cross-domain data-flow towards a thriving data-driven EU economy.

I-BiDaaS will shift the power balance within an organisation, increase efficiency, reduce costs, improve employee empowerment and increase profitability. Moreover, I-BiDaaS will deliver a full array of big data business analytics solutions for structured, unstructured, noisy and potentially synthetic data for companies in multiple industries that are more accessible, cost effective and employee-empowering than existing solutions, which gives companies the confidence to deploy Big Data Self-Service solutions across the organisation, from consumer-facing employees with little IT experience or expertise to top management and helps companies to optimize decision-making at the tactical, operational and strategic levels.

2.5.2.16. Ocean Decade Heritage Network

<https://www.oceandecadeheritage.org/>

In 2017, UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) was tasked by the UN General Assembly to develop a focused approach to addressing multiple stressors on global marine systems and manage them sustainably through ocean observations and research. The resulting Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030 is a large-scale UN initiative that promotes a common framework for supporting ocean stakeholders in studying and assessing the health of the world's oceans. The intended outcomes are "to predict the consequences of change, design mitigation, and guide adaptation" and to "ensure ocean science can fully support countries in creating improved conditions for sustainable development of the Ocean", complementing the UN's Sustainable Development Goal 14 "Life below Water".

The Ocean Decade Heritage Network has the dual aims of raising awareness in the cultural heritage community about the UN's Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030 and coordinating a targeted global response from the community to improve the integration of archaeology and cultural heritage management within the marine sciences during the Decade's Preparatory (2018-20) and Implementation Phases (2021-30).

2.5.2.17. PSLifeStyle

<https://pslifestyle.eu/>

PSLifestyle is closing the gap between climate awareness and individual action. PSLifestyle will inspire the audience to adopt a positive, sustainable, and healthier lifestyle by helping them reduce their environmental impact. The PSL tool will help the users get informed about the environmental impact of their day-to-day activities and will inspire them to think about their current habits and how they could be changed through smart everyday actions. So, they will get the chance to develop their personalised plans and keep track of their progress.

2.5.2.18. ENALIATEC

<https://enaliathec.com/>

EnaliaTec is a private capital company based in Thessaloniki involved in the research and development of underwater technologies, providing integrated software and hardware solutions for the marine environment

EnaliaTec was selected after an Open Call evaluation process under the Underwater thematic focus. The collaboration among parties was formalized by the signature of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), aiming to drive the co-design and delivery of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in Underwater research.

The supply and development of their solutions and services is based on the know-how of the team of the laboratory of virtual and augmented reality of CERTH-IPTI acquired in the framework of research projects.

2.5.2.19. DESIRA

<https://desira2020.eu/>

DESIRA (Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas) is a Horizon 2020 project (2019-2023) coordinated by the University of Pisa which involves 25 partner organisations (research institutes, NGOs and SMEs) in a multi-actor and inter-disciplinary Consortium. The project aims to improve the capacity of society and political bodies to respond to the challenges that digitalisation generates in agriculture, forestry and rural areas.

2.5.2.20. EOSC Future

<https://eoscfuture.eu/>

EOSC FUTURE is a H2020 project funded by the European Commission that is implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). EOSC will give European researchers access to a wide web of FAIR data and related services. The project will adopt a system-of-systems approach to the EOSC platform, linking together other research portals, resources and services to respond to the data needs of a wide range of researchers.

During the lifetime of EOSC FUTURE, the project partners will work with key stakeholders to ensure a smooth user experience, developing (i) EOSC core, the set of enabling services needed to operate the EOSC; (ii) EOSC exchange registering resources and services from research infrastructures, other EOSC projects and science clusters to the EOSC and integrating them with the EOSC core functionalities and (iii) the EOSC interoperability framework will provide guidelines for providers that want to integrate services or data into EOSC.

2.5.2.21. OWL

<https://ourwatchleads.com/>

OWL (Our Watch Leads) is a startup, specialized in the transfer of Satellite Earth Observation Technology, applied to the construction and real estate sectors. OWL, one of the selected applicants of the NEANIAS 1ST Open Call, aims to (i) create value for the customer, to know the markets and the territories of intervention, (ii) create innovative and sustainable solutions in the social, environmental and economic fields and (iii) being in the reference Architecture and Engineering market, earning the customer's preference.

2.5.2.22. SANTORY

<https://santory.gr/>

SANTORY is an ambitious, multi-disciplinary research project which seeks to provide solutions to understanding and mitigating future, potentially disastrous, impacts of explosive volcanic eruptions, landslides of hydrothermally weakened volcanic edifices, earthquakes (with probable consequent tsunamis), and the release of heavy and potentially hazardous metals in the water column. SANTORY will establish a cutting-edge seafloor observatory using innovative marine technology within the most-active submarine Mediterranean volcano, Kolumbo. It will build an open-access data hub using

innovative visualization and virtual reality technologies to present the volcanic dynamics driving scientific knowledge advances and communicating hazards to the society in easy-to-understand ways. The outcomes of SANTORY will provide the impetus for much needed multidisciplinary collaboration in Greece and across the EU and will be a first step for understanding of such natural laboratories to underpin development of next-generation shallow volcanic seafloor observatories.

2.5.2.23. GEO Insight

<https://www.geoinsight.hu/>

GEOInsight is a start-up business formed to commercially utilise a set of software and procedural solutions (the “GEOInsight Solution”), originally developed at the Research Centre for Astronomy and Earth Sciences of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, specifically to support the analysis of population distributions on the basis of cellular data generated by mobile telephone system operators.

2.5.3. Agreements signed

Different agreements have been signed to formalize the relationship between NEANIAS and other projects and initiatives, thus expressing the objectives and scope of the collaborations

The following table shows the agreements signed.

3 rd Party	Type of Agreement
HCMR	MOU
Blue Cloud	Collaboration agreement in specific topics
EOSC Future	Letter of support
RAMONES	MOU
SANTORY	MOU
TRIPLE	MOU
ENALIA TEC	MOU
GEO Insight	MOU
INODE	MOU
OWL	MOU
DESIRA	Letter of support
PS Lifestyle	Letter of support

Table 11 Agreements signed

3. WP10 Organization

3.1. Coordination Model

The Outreach Task Force is created to lead and coordinate Dissemination activities. The composition of the Outreach Task Force is based on the Grant Agreement and is led by Outreach Manager and engages partners with key roles in outreach WPs. Next chart illustrates the model.

Fig. 103 Coordination model

The role of the team is to monitor outreach activities, identify opportunities and mobilise resources, as outreach in NEANIAS is quite intensive, ambitious and of strategic importance for the success of the project. WP10 is composed of all project members, who were requested to contribute with their knowledge and networking, as well as the specific tasks in charge.

3.2. Coordination activities

The Communication, Dissemination, Engagement and Dissemination WP means a cross-task throughout the life of the project that involves all partners. To lead and coordinate the activities, the WP leader has established the following means:

- WP 10 working group
- WP 10 committee
- Project meetings
- On demand meetings

3.2.1. WP 10 working group

To organize and manage the WP-10 activities, a working group has been created, made up of a representative from each partner. This group, which constitutes the executive committee of the WP 10, meets monthly, the third Friday of each month. The agenda always contains the following points:

- Overview
- Activity per WP, considering dissemination activities (already done and planned), articles and contents.
- Risks
- Actions for next month
- KPIs status
- Next steps

Moreover, any particular issue is discussed considering the needs (for instance, the production of newsletter, the organization or participation in any event, collaboration with other projects and liaison activities, actions for the Open Call, legal issues, training needs, concerns, ...).

The next pictures illustrate some content discussed in the meetings.

- Document template used for presentations in WP10 meetings:

Fig. 104 WP10 monthly meeting. Example (1)

- Example of agenda of topics to be discussed in a WP 10 meeting.

Fig. 105 WP10 monthly meeting. Example (2)

- Following, sample of presentation and subsequent discussion on the contents of NEANIAS website and how to maximize the impact on our audience.

Fig. 106 WP10 monthly meeting. Example (3)

- Following, an example about the use and impacts of NEANIAS digital channels.

Fig. 107 WP10 monthly meeting. Example (4)

The next figure illustrates a discussion about the organization of EOSC project expo:

EOSC Projects EXPO
16-19 November 2020
CALL FOR EXHIBITORS: 6 NOV DEADLINE

Organised by: EOSC hub, ECHO, SSHOC

Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences, humanities and beyond

- ✓ Liaison with other H2020.
- ✓ MoUs with 3rd parties
- ✓ Ecosystem knowledge
- ✓ Commercial exploitation
- WP02, WP03 WP04
- WP05 Innovation
- WP06 Core
- WP07 Delivery
- WP08 EOSC
- WP09 Sustainability
- WP10 Dissemination

Fig. 108 WP10 monthly meeting. Example (5)

3.2.2. WP 10 Committee

To ensure that the entire project is well represented, and the workload is well balanced among all members, some tasks have been coordinated among the leaders of the NEANIAS work packages. Then, each of the WP leaders has managed internally among their members the best way to achieve the challenges purposed:

- Production of articles and contents.
- Representative content for the newsletter.
- Stakeholders' engagement.
- Collaboration with other projects.
- Participation in thematic events.
- Integration with other digital platforms.

3.2.3. Project meetings

The project meetings, both of the Project Management Board and the Plenary Meetings, have been very fruitful in communication, interaction, engagement and planning of actions involving WP10. They have also been a place to discuss follow-up, share achievements, and communicate general messages.

The pictures below illustrate it:

Day 3rd September

Link: <https://global.gotomeeting.com/join/416492573>

<i>Technical, Managerial and Business sessions</i>		
Start Time	Session Title and Info	Presenters / Moderators/Contributors
9:00 - 11:00 CE9T	Discussion on the thematic /core services open issues (cont.)	Chair: Prof. K. Karantzas (SSCCo), G. Kakaletis (TM), WP leaders, Task leaders
11:00 - 12:00	WP 1,10: Management issues (Administrative & Financial aspects), Management tools, KPIs, Dissemination issues - Discussion	Chair: Prof. M. Hatzopoulos, E. Petra, Dr. N. Chondros (NKUA), Dr. Daniel Martinez (RICOH),
12:00 - 14:00	Lunch break	
14:00 - 15:00	WP 5, WP9: Business cases, Assessment and Sustainability issues	Chair: Dr. K. Kovacs (INNOMINE), Dr. I. Neokosmides (INCITES)
15:00 - 16:00	Discussion on the Business cases, Assessment and Sustainability issues	WPs, WP9 Workpackage leaders, Task leaders NEANIAS partners
16:00 - 17:00	Focused group meetings (optional – parallel sessions)	
17:00	End of meeting	

Fig. 109 Plenary meeting and WP10 (example 1)

Wednesday 27 November

<i>Introduction and kicking off of all activities</i>		
Start Time	Session Title and Info	Presenters / Contributors
09:00	Welcome & Round Table	Prof. M. Roussopoulos (NKUA), All
09:40	Project objectives	Prof. M. Roussopoulos (NKUA), E.Petra (NKUA)
10:10	Contribution to EOSC strategy and goals	Dr. G. Papastefanatos (ATHENA)
10:40	Under Water Research Sector	Prof. P. Nomikou (NKUA)
11:05	Coffee break	
11:25	Space Research Sector	Dr. E. Sciacca (INAF)
11:50	Atmosphere Research Sector	Prof. S. Rapsomanikis (ATHENA)
12:15	Core Services	Dr. R. Lovas (SZTAKI)
12:40	Engagement of the 3 Sector Communities	Dr. U. Becciani (INAF)
13:10	Lunch	
14:10	Data Management Plan, IPR and Licensing	G. Kakalettris (CITE)
14:30	Communication, Dissemination & Outreach	D. Martinez (RICOH)
15:00	Exploitation and Sustainability	Th. Rokkas (INCITES)
15:20	Innovation Issues and Actions	Dr. K. Kovacs (INNOMINE)
15:40	Management organization, tools & procedures	N. Chondros (NKUA), G. Kakalettris (CITE)
16:10	Coffee break	
16:30	Consortium agreement, Administrative & Financial aspects	M. Hatzopoulos (NKUA), K. Papadaki (NKUA)
17:00	Quality Assurance & Risk Management	G. Kakalettris (CITE) / K.Kakalettris (CITE)
17:30	End of the day	
19:00	Social Dinner	

Fig. 110 Plenary meeting and WP10 (example 2)

And then some illustrative images about the face-to-face (before the pandemic) and virtual meetings.

Fig. 111 NEANIAS meeting (1)

Fig. 112 NEANIAS meeting (2)

Fig. 113 NEANIAS meeting (3)

Fig. 114 NEANIAS meeting (4)

3.2.4. On demand meetings

In addition to all the above, several meetings have been held on demand in order to manage particular issues related to the objectives of WP. The meetings, requested by the WP-10 leader or any project member, could have been at the member level, the WP level, or with several representatives to discuss a certain matter, such as:

- KPIs discussions.
- Production of content.
- Participation in an event.
- Publishing on media.
- Analysis of contingencies.
- Stakeholder engagement.
- Networking and user attraction.
- Training needs in digital channels.
- Digital resources needs.
- IT integrations.
- Dissemination material needs.
- Content in other national languages.
- Joint collaboration in relevant task (open call, reports, ...)
- Etc.

3.2.5. Main meetings

As executive summary, next table displays the main meetings held at project level.

Meeting	Place and date
WP10 Teleconference	online monthly meeting
Project Management Board meeting	online monthly meeting
General meeting	Online, Nov 4, 2019
General meeting	Athens, Nov 27-29, 2019
General meeting	Online, March 18-19, 2020
General meeting	Online, September 2-3, 2020
General meeting	Online, November 19-20, 2020
General meeting	Online, March 29-30, 2021
General meeting	Sicily, June 5-7, 2021
General meeting	Online, February 17-18, 2022
General meeting	Budapest, May 10-12, 2022
General meeting	Online, September 08, 2022
Open Event	Barcelona, September 22-23, 2022
General meeting	Athens, October 25-27, 2022

Table 12 Main meetings (executive)

4. WP10 Summary and conclusions

This final section presents the impact and the results achieved during the project.

The COVID-19 pandemic erupted fully in the 4th month of the project's life, with all the limitations that it entailed for dissemination activities (confinements, cancellation of events, mobility restrictions, budgetary restrictions of companies for travel or attendance at events ...). However, a contingency plan was carried out, reorganizing the schedules, the activities and strongly promoting digital activity to achieve the initial objectives.

The project has had a wide audience, both by the ecosystem and by a general public. Internally, all the partners have actively participated and contributed, favouring a rich, transversal and multidisciplinary presentation of the challenges and results of the project, thus reaching multiple sectors, markets and communities. A continuous coordination and engagement model has made it possible to maintain a high level of dynamism in the dissemination of various, quality and interesting content.

Next charts show the impact of the communication and dissemination activities considering the profile of the people and the means.

Fig. 115 Dissemination impact by profile (left) and channel (right)

Considering all possible means and audiences, it can be said that the project has aroused interest or has been known in some way on more than 800.000 times. The greatest groups are the general public and the civil society, mainly due to the general dissemination on social media and the digital channels, also at worldwide level, as shown in the website impact map. Digital channels represented the point of contact for the project in 76% of cases.

The scientific community and industry were also contacted through these channels, but also more specifically through all NEANIAS activities such as workshops, conferences, fairs, exhibitions, webinars, courses, datathons and hackathons, the NEANIAS Open Calls and the NEANIAS Open Event.

Various specific meetings were also organized to present the project, mainly to policy makers, investors or the media. These meetings were normally individual and personalized.

Regarding the position of people interested in NEANIAS, we cannot have general data, but the information obtained from the NEANIAS Open Event offers a good representation.

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Fig. 116 Impact by position (estimation)

The NEANIAS audience has a very good representation at all levels: scientific, technical, business and management.

The same criteria can be applied to have an estimate of the gender of people. About 2 out of 3 people interested in NEANIAS are male.

Fig. 117 Impact by gender (estimation)

The following tables summarizes the indicators of success of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. Many of the values far exceed the initial goals. The detail is presented in Report of Activities section above.

1. KPI's concerning user (supply and demand) attraction:

Range	Dissemination and communication activities	Target	Result
Ecosystem	Workshops / conferences (co)organized.	9	29
Ecosystem	Workshops supported by presenters and panellists on project specific topics.	30	45

Table 13 KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction.

2. KPIs concerning innovation dissemination:

Range	Dissemination and communication activities	Target	Result
Ecosystem	Open calls applicants/participants	30	27

Table 14 KPIs concerning innovation dissemination

3. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination:

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Range	Dissemination and communication activities	Target	Result
Wide range	Average social media posts per month	8	40
Wide range	General public articles languages supported	9	10
Ecosystem	Peer reviewed scientific publications	25	26
Ecosystem	Other scientific publications and artifacts	30	60
Ecosystem	References and acknowledgements	100	13
Ecosystem	Whitepapers (as per work plan)	4	4
Ecosystem	Multimedia & training material published	30	40
Ecosystem	Gold Open Access publications percentage	30%	20%
Wide range	Fairs and exhibitions participated	20	22
Wide range	Commercial exploitation events participation	10	17

Table 15 KPIs concerning scientific dissemination

4. KPIs concerning social dissemination:

Range	Dissemination and communication activities	Target	Result
Wide range	Websites launched (workplan)	1	1
Wide range	Website content updating (average)	weekly	2,7 per week
Ecosystem	Templates for dissemination activities and other premade dissemination material	10	12
Ecosystem	Hardcopy/tangible material forms	5	23
Wide range	Social media dissemination channels	4	4
Wide range	Social media impressions (social media channels total)	30.000	340.000
Wide range	Social media followers (total across media)	2.000	2.424
Wide range	Average technical blog posts per month	4	5,7
Wide range	Average general public blog posts per month	4	5,9
Wide range	General public articles on printed or online media	30	35
Wide range	Newsletters issued (biannual)	6	6

Table 16 KPIs concerning social dissemination

5. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts:

Range	Dissemination and communication activities	Target	Result
Ecosystem	Relevant H2020 Projects & research infrastructures liaised with NEANIAS (total)	20	26
Ecosystem	Projects & initiatives liaised with, from the same call, sharing experiences and solutions to challenges.	3	3

Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report.

Ecosystem	MoUs signed with 3rd parties.	10	11
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons organized by the project	4	4
Ecosystem	3rd party datathons/hackathons supported by project	4	4
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons participants	500	410
Ecosystem	Individuals directly addressed via scientific, academic communication, innovation stimulation, training and engagement activities	3000	8500

Table 17 KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OTF	Outreach task force
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web